

Supplementary material to “*Determinants of phonetic word duration in ten language documentation corpora: Word frequency, complexity, position, and part of speech*”

by

*Jan Strunk, Frank Seifart, Swintha Danielsen, Iren Hartman, Brigitte Pakendorf,
Søren Wichmann, Alena Witzlack-Makarevich & Balthasar Bickel*

Contents

A. Lists of the 100 most frequent word types in the ten languages	2
B. Lists of excluded word types in the ten languages	35
C. Distribution of word frequencies (Zipf plots)	43
D. Details on the individual mixed-effects models for the ten languages	44

A. Lists of the 100 most frequent word types in the ten languages

Table 1: The 100 most frequent word types in Baure

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	ro = kich -wo =ro =ji	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3SGm = QUOT	V	182	0.0104	1.0	11	0.6656	0.1462	18.7880	3.7824
2	ri = kich -wo =ro =ji	3SGf = say.do -COP = 3SGm = QUOT	V	100	0.0057	2.0	7	0.6916	0.1168	17.8766	3.2307
3	ro = kich -wo =ri =ji	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3SGf = QUOT	V	53	0.0030	3.0	5	0.6681	0.1154	19.1946	3.2702
4	showekon	jaguar	N	50	0.0028	4.0	4	0.6174	0.1188	13.4708	2.9886
5	ro = kich -wo =ro	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3SGm	V	46	0.0026	5.0	12	0.5265	0.1845	20.5425	5.0174
6	shiyé'	fox	N	43	0.0024	6.0	2	0.4438	0.1472	14.5110	3.8179
7	monchi	child	N	40	0.0023	7.0	7	0.4939	0.0956	12.5991	2.5166
8	kewon	come!	V	36	0.0020	8.0	10	0.4126	0.1322	13.0397	3.1770
9	ro = shim	3SGm = arrive	V	35	0.0020	9.5	14	0.4595	0.0884	13.6509	2.5893
10	ni = shir	1SG = son	N	35	0.0020	9.5	7	0.5066	0.1554	12.7946	3.3592
11	ni = tori	1SG = friend	N	34	0.0019	11.0	5	0.4409	0.1049	11.9288	2.6810
12	jir	man	N	33	0.0019	12.5	11	0.2692	0.0915	12.7145	5.1769
13	ro = nik	3SGm = eat	V	33	0.0019	12.5	9	0.4398	0.1253	12.2197	3.2267
14	eton	woman	N	31	0.0018	14.5	8	0.5831	0.2930	7.8026	2.4783
15	ro = en	3SGm = mother	N	31	0.0018	14.5	3	0.4316	0.1187	7.3779	1.6965
16	kew	go.IMP	V	30	0.0017	16.0	9	0.2964	0.1887	13.0170	5.8393
17	mamit	mum	N	29	0.0017	17.0	6	0.4828	0.0950	10.6755	1.7150
18	ni = ki'in -wo	1SG = want -COP	V	27	0.0015	18.0	13	0.5603	0.2546	16.4188	5.3770
19	in	water	N	26	0.0015	19.5	8	0.3562	0.0974	6.2652	2.2873
20	ka'an	animal	N	26	0.0015	19.5	7	0.4423	0.1236	11.9598	2.5759
21	lor	parrot	N	24	0.0014	21.0	1	0.4175	0.0860	7.4804	1.5346
22	kach	go	V	23	0.0013	22.5	9	0.2530	0.0694	17.6219	4.7088
23	kove'	dog	N	23	0.0013	22.5	4	0.5217	0.2325	10.9134	3.5867
24	chindi -nev	person -PL	N	22	0.0013	24.0	11	0.6841	0.1367	13.6188	2.4803
25	aren	bird	N	21	0.0012	25.5	6	0.5254	0.1177	8.0215	1.9750
26	ni = piri	1SG = sibling.of.same.sex	N	21	0.0012	25.5	5	0.6435	0.2290	10.4664	3.6373
27	ni = kach	1SG = go	V	19	0.0011	28.5	9	0.5048	0.2440	12.4085	3.8248
28	ri = avinon	3SGf = husband	N	19	0.0011	28.5	7	0.6154	0.1476	13.7184	3.2136
29	mochach	youngster	N	19	0.0011	28.5	5	0.6326	0.1527	11.6213	2.5277
30	sipori	frog	N	19	0.0011	28.5	3	0.5284	0.0799	11.5939	1.6898
31	senior	lord	N	18	0.0010	32.5	7	0.5897	0.2323	11.4206	3.6685
32	ro = kach -po -wo	3SGm = go -PFV.REFL -COP	V	18	0.0010	32.5	6	0.6246	0.1125	14.8557	2.6788
33	no = shim	3PL = arrive	V	18	0.0010	32.5	5	0.5156	0.1604	12.8417	4.4705
34	no = kich -wo =ro =ji	3PL = say.do -COP = 3SGm = QUOT	V	18	0.0010	32.5	4	0.7644	0.1305	16.0767	2.3856
35	kajap	manioc	N	17	0.0010	35.5	6	0.5498	0.1995	9.9515	5.4620
36	kach -wo =ji	go -COP = QUOT	V	17	0.0010	35.5	5	0.5524	0.1092	14.9121	2.4107
37	pi = kach	2SG = go	V	16	0.0009	39.0	9	0.5271	0.1674	12.8207	5.5378
38	pi = nik	2SG = eat	V	16	0.0009	39.0	6	0.4639	0.1482	11.7910	3.5791
39	shim	arrive	V	16	0.0009	39.0	4	0.3700	0.0808	11.4983	2.6507
40	ni = kich -wo =ro	1SG = say.do -COP = 3SGm	V	16	0.0009	39.0	2	0.5989	0.1931	16.4167	4.9201

Table 1: The 100 most frequent word types in Baure (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
41	ri = piri	3SGf = sibling.of.same.sex	N	16	0.0009	39.0	2	0.5804	0.1364	10.9856	3.0061
42	kach -po -wo	go -PFV.REFL -COP	V	15	0.0009	44.0	9	0.5650	0.0947	12.6930	1.9971
43	ro = kich -wo = ni	3SGm = say.do -COP = 1SG	V	15	0.0009	44.0	3	0.7703	0.2262	15.2725	3.9293
44	tiporek	chicken	N	15	0.0009	44.0	3	0.5887	0.1128	12.2736	2.1648
45	ni = kombar	1SG = fellow	N	15	0.0009	44.0	3	0.6330	0.1584	12.1920	3.3960
46	aboel	grandparent	N	15	0.0009	44.0	1	0.4743	0.1437	11.5614	3.8287
47	ro = epen	3SGm = die	V	14	0.0008	50.5	8	0.5644	0.1161	9.6170	2.2393
48	sorati -ye	village -LOC	N	14	0.0008	50.5	7	0.7539	0.0963	10.7723	1.3594
49	ro = kich -wo	3SGm = say.do -COP	V	14	0.0008	50.5	6	0.4321	0.0880	19.2326	3.8616
50	ka'an -nev	animal -PL	N	14	0.0008	50.5	4	0.6043	0.1223	15.4606	3.1614
51	chach	father	N	14	0.0008	50.5	3	0.4336	0.1789	14.1473	7.4654
52	ro = kicho -wo = ri = ji	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3SGf = QUOT	V	14	0.0008	50.5	3	0.7279	0.1519	18.5164	3.4304
53	vi = kach	1PL = go	V	14	0.0008	50.5	2	0.5816	0.1805	11.6228	4.9682
54	no = pijik	3PL = pass	V	14	0.0008	50.5	2	0.5516	0.0780	12.8988	1.6065
55	ri = kicho -wo = ro	3SGf = say.do -COP = 3SGm	V	13	0.0007	57.5	8	0.5400	0.0977	19.2055	4.2276
56	poewok -ye	ground -LOC	N	13	0.0007	57.5	8	0.6970	0.2634	14.1633	3.9421
57	ro = eyon	3SGm = wife	N	13	0.0007	57.5	7	0.5981	0.1685	9.8101	3.4878
58	kanikon	food	N	13	0.0007	57.5	6	0.6037	0.1020	11.8555	1.6911
59	kicho -wo = ro = ji	say.do -COP = 3SGm = QUOT	V	13	0.0007	57.5	6	0.6555	0.1907	16.2708	3.9656
60	livor	book	N	13	0.0007	57.5	1	0.4715	0.1156	11.2461	2.8943
61	pi = ki'in -wo	2SG = want -COP	V	12	0.0007	64.5	6	0.4755	0.0744	19.3273	2.8231
62	ro = via	3SGm = take.away	V	12	0.0007	64.5	6	0.4159	0.2771	16.3561	6.6983
63	ro = siap	3SGm = enter	V	12	0.0007	64.5	6	0.4967	0.0951	13.3470	2.7674
64	vekiyiri	god	N	12	0.0007	64.5	5	0.6208	0.1414	13.4375	2.7069
65	simori -nev	pig -PL	N	12	0.0007	64.5	5	0.8180	0.3089	12.1827	3.6165
66	koshapoe'	banana	N	12	0.0007	64.5	2	0.7183	0.1284	12.8968	2.2962
67	kes	cheese	N	12	0.0007	64.5	2	0.4733	0.1802	6.9595	1.8743
68	novia'	bride	N	12	0.0007	64.5	1	0.4533	0.1342	14.3808	4.4877
69	ro = nik -pa	3SGm = eat -INTL	V	11	0.0006	71.5	7	0.6273	0.1122	11.4912	2.0656
70	ro = shim = ji	3SGm = arrive = QUOT	V	11	0.0006	71.5	6	0.6018	0.0994	13.6121	2.1517
71	choros	sweetcorn	N	11	0.0006	71.5	4	0.5130	0.1132	12.2196	2.7104
72	ro = kich -wo = ri	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3SGf	V	11	0.0006	71.5	3	0.5255	0.1456	21.4027	4.0315
73	pi = nik -pa -no	2SG = eat -INTL -NMLZ	V	11	0.0006	71.5	3	0.6164	0.0830	13.2019	1.8338
74	jawpa'	soap	N	11	0.0006	71.5	1	0.4131	0.1127	7.6029	1.4392
75	wapoer -ye	river -LOC	N	10	0.0006	82.5	7	0.6565	0.1181	14.1345	2.6874
76	no = kach	3PL = go	V	10	0.0006	82.5	7	0.5157	0.1743	12.7286	3.7451
77	ro = epshe	3SGm = appear	V	10	0.0006	82.5	6	0.5468	0.1389	12.1996	3.0996
78	ro = erotorok	3SGm = leave	V	10	0.0006	82.5	5	0.5669	0.0851	12.5882	1.7962
79	ses	sun	N	10	0.0006	82.5	5	0.5341	0.2228	6.3121	1.9422
80	ekosh	manioc.plant	N	10	0.0006	82.5	4	0.6475	0.1184	7.9943	1.7153
81	seman	week	N	10	0.0006	82.5	4	0.5545	0.1299	9.4522	2.1267
82	kiwor	snake	N	10	0.0006	82.5	4	0.5587	0.1395	9.4350	2.2028

Table 1: The 100 most frequent word types in Baure (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
83	ni = en	1SG = mother	N	10	0.0006	82.5	4	0.4486	0.1476	7.4953	2.8682
84	ri = shir	3SGf = son	N	10	0.0006	82.5	3	0.5265	0.0952	11.7460	2.1773
85	ro = pino -po	3SGm = flee -PFV.REFL	V	10	0.0006	82.5	3	0.5141	0.1232	14.2970	3.2613
86	marok	chicha	N	10	0.0006	82.5	2	0.5630	0.1182	9.4054	1.9403
87	kikoe	really.believe	V	10	0.0006	82.5	2	0.5380	0.2346	12.3429	4.9266
88	echomoe'	peel	N	10	0.0006	82.5	1	0.5520	0.1400	15.4154	4.2069
89	ri = kicho -wo =ri =ji	3SGf = say.do -COP = 3SGf = QUOT	V	10	0.0006	82.5	1	0.6720	0.2714	21.2992	5.9970
90	irja'	partridge	N	10	0.0006	82.5	1	0.5800	0.2583	7.7483	2.2313
91	ro = kach	3SGm = go	V	9	0.0005	99.0	7	0.4532	0.1718	14.9449	4.8260
92	ni = jin	1SG = daughter	N	9	0.0005	99.0	6	0.4987	0.1905	12.1645	6.5976
93	ro = imok	3SGm = sleep	V	9	0.0005	99.0	6	0.5683	0.1658	11.1906	3.8518
94	ri = shim	3SGf = arrive	V	9	0.0005	99.0	6	0.6106	0.1388	10.5749	3.0712
95	ro = ki'in -wo	3SGm = want -COP	V	9	0.0005	99.0	6	0.6132	0.4096	69.0395	161.6719
96	ro = nik -wo	3SGm = eat -COP	V	9	0.0005	99.0	6	0.5511	0.0649	12.8753	1.6692
97	ro = wer	3SGm = house	N	9	0.0005	99.0	5	0.5540	0.1704	9.8353	3.2024
98	ri = shechenev	3SGf = children	N	9	0.0005	99.0	4	0.8428	0.1927	13.7472	2.8539
99	sopir	tortoise	N	9	0.0005	99.0	3	0.5886	0.1559	8.9414	1.9930
100	ro = kich -wo =no =ji	3SGm = say.do -COP = 3PL = QUOT	V	9	0.0005	99.0	2	0.8293	0.3632	15.9956	4.1291

Table 2: The 100 most frequent word types in Bora

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	nee -vbe	say -M.SG	V	276	0.0096	1.0	20	0.3680	0.1099	15.1716	5.9358
2	nee -lle	say -F.SG	V	111	0.0039	2.0	14	0.3388	0.1215	22.5359	21.4352
3	nee -vbe -va -pe	say -M.SG -QUOT -REM	V	75	0.0026	3.0	11	0.6503	0.1861	16.5725	7.4686
4	pañe -vu	inside -ALL	N	68	0.0024	4.0	23	0.3969	0.1121	15.9047	5.4212
5	pee -ne	go -INAN	V	61	0.0021	5.0	16	0.3711	0.1166	16.5264	6.6282
6	pañe	inside	N	59	0.0021	6.0	19	0.2823	0.1026	17.4021	10.9630
7	nee	say	V	58	0.0020	7.0	24	0.2008	0.0663	16.7147	6.7453
8	i- nee -ne	3- say -INAN	V	57	0.0020	8.0	14	0.3719	0.1022	17.4993	5.5253
9	muúbe	brother	N	55	0.0019	9.5	18	0.4288	0.1622	13.6516	6.6395
10	pee -vbe	go -M.SG	V	55	0.0019	9.5	17	0.4491	0.1390	12.4233	4.9507
11	taalléu	grandmother	N	49	0.0017	11.0	5	0.4007	0.1251	18.5799	19.9453
12	nee -du	say -CMPV	V	48	0.0017	12.0	13	0.3227	0.0844	16.7514	5.1035
13	múnaa	people	N	47	0.0016	13.0	17	0.3407	0.0893	15.6637	4.3100
14	nee -hi	say -PRED	V	45	0.0016	14.5	15	0.4534	0.1116	13.8179	3.6403
15	pee	go	V	45	0.0016	14.5	13	0.2135	0.0796	16.2424	7.1560
16	úmeco	anger	N	44	0.0015	16.0	8	0.3951	0.1034	13.5329	3.7288
17	táhdif	grandfather	N	42	0.0015	17.0	11	0.4214	0.0776	12.6851	2.4555
18	mewa	wife	N	39	0.0014	18.0	9	0.3508	0.1097	15.4816	8.9808
19	nee -lle -va -pe	say -F.SG -QUOT -REM	V	38	0.0013	19.0	9	0.6254	0.2045	20.2018	13.3112
20	éлле -vu	there -ALL	N	37	0.0013	20.5	15	0.3384	0.1000	19.9451	6.3933
21	tsaa -vbe	come -M.SG	V	37	0.0013	20.5	11	0.4714	0.1218	13.7331	4.0697
22	úújete	reach	V	35	0.0012	22.0	14	0.4194	0.1477	21.4708	34.1561
23	niimúhe	God	N	34	0.0012	23.5	9	0.5020	0.1354	15.0963	4.8955
24	tsífmene	child	N	34	0.0012	23.5	8	0.4681	0.1187	18.2536	5.6696
25	nee -ne	say -INAN	V	32	0.0011	25.0	14	0.3700	0.1335	15.9238	5.8739
26	nuhba	sun	N	29	0.0010	26.0	8	0.3858	0.1108	14.6364	6.5115
27	teéhi	river	N	28	0.0010	28.5	7	0.2408	0.0420	17.6758	3.1724
28	májcho -ta	eat -NMZ	V	28	0.0010	28.5	5	0.6113	0.1316	13.6380	2.7242
29	waháro -j	mother -VOC	N	28	0.0010	28.5	4	0.3210	0.0857	16.6565	4.3624
30	wájyá	spirit	N	28	0.0010	28.5	2	0.2940	0.0788	18.2094	4.7873
31	meenu -ne	do -INAN	V	27	0.0009	33.0	17	0.4753	0.1008	15.4189	3.4432
32	nee -me	say -PL	V	27	0.0009	33.0	12	0.3298	0.1414	18.9786	8.9591
33	waháro	mother	N	27	0.0009	33.0	7	0.3291	0.1506	17.7788	11.2999
34	pee -híjcyá -vbe	go -REP -M.SG	V	27	0.0009	33.0	5	0.7613	0.2458	16.7567	8.8280
35	ífbii	coca	N	27	0.0009	33.0	5	0.5397	0.1169	9.6435	1.8912
36	nú -jpacyó	water -CLF.liquid	N	26	0.0009	37.0	11	0.5592	0.1543	15.1889	3.4660
37	nee -vbe -re -va -pe	say -M.SG -REST -QUOT -REM	V	26	0.0009	37.0	6	0.6614	0.1289	15.7699	3.5834
38	úmeco	war	N	26	0.0009	37.0	3	0.3465	0.0782	15.1317	3.3409
39	pee -hi	go -PRED	V	25	0.0009	39.5	5	0.3323	0.1093	21.6689	24.1082
40	ívaké	ívaké	N	25	0.0009	39.5	2	0.3872	0.1384	12.1316	2.9621
41	tsaa	come	V	24	0.0008	41.5	10	0.2574	0.0956	17.6465	10.2245
42	llif	son	N	24	0.0008	41.5	8	0.3524	0.2347	15.7847	5.8652
43	májcho	eat	V	23	0.0008	44.5	8	0.5237	0.1306	12.1109	2.9285

Table 2: The 100 most frequent word types in Bora (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	tsijju	mother	N	23	0.0008	44.5	8	0.3426	0.0858	18.6604	4.9521
45	doo -hi	eat_meat -PRED	V	23	0.0008	44.5	7	0.5008	0.3275	14.7141	6.8511
46	pee -lle	go -F.SG	V	23	0.0008	44.5	2	0.4383	0.1434	16.2617	9.4854
47	i- ujcu -ne	3- get -INAN	V	22	0.0008	47.0	10	0.4544	0.1528	17.6054	7.7698
48	pee -hijcya	go -REP	V	21	0.0007	50.0	8	0.5163	0.1985	18.6553	11.2169
49	meenu	do	V	21	0.0007	50.0	7	0.3297	0.1237	17.3884	7.6074
50	pee -juco	go -AFIR	V	21	0.0007	50.0	6	0.5284	0.1816	14.9762	5.5472
51	pee -juco -vbe	go -AFIR -M.SG	V	21	0.0007	50.0	3	0.8043	0.1287	11.4836	1.9451
52	majcho -ta -he	eat -NMZ -CLF.tree	V	21	0.0007	50.0	2	0.9062	0.1387	11.3070	1.5454
53	úújete -vbe	reach -M.SG	V	20	0.0007	54.0	6	0.7157	0.1346	13.0295	2.6074
54	ta- tsímene	1SG.POSS- child	N	20	0.0007	54.0	5	0.6414	0.1234	17.7175	3.6861
55	muúlle	sister	N	20	0.0007	54.0	3	0.3923	0.0897	16.1678	4.3069
56	tsaa -me	come -PL	V	19	0.0007	57.5	8	0.4887	0.2082	14.0328	4.6332
57	nee -vbe -re	say -M.SG -REST	V	19	0.0007	57.5	8	0.4542	0.1413	16.8796	5.5811
58	bóóa	boa	N	19	0.0007	57.5	3	0.2726	0.0479	15.1148	2.7299
59	íju	anteater	N	19	0.0007	57.5	2	0.5748	0.2325	7.9488	2.7650
60	hallu -vu	on -ALL	N	18	0.0006	60.0	8	0.3599	0.1174	21.7161	9.6921
61	nee -ne -líihye	say -INAN -BEN	V	17	0.0006	62.5	8	0.4435	0.1110	21.3328	7.0225
62	doo -ne	eat_meat -INAN	V	17	0.0006	62.5	6	0.3889	0.0931	13.8978	3.0645
63	bájcu	bone	N	17	0.0006	62.5	2	0.5262	0.1250	9.9793	2.2368
64	vúúrfhif	frog	N	17	0.0006	62.5	1	0.4219	0.1161	15.5561	3.2947
65	nee -hijcya -ne	say -REP -INAN	V	16	0.0006	67.5	8	0.4572	0.2030	28.2083	17.2537
66	uubálle	story	N	16	0.0006	67.5	7	0.5321	0.1173	13.7433	2.9108
67	pañe -tu	inside -ABL	N	16	0.0006	67.5	7	0.4169	0.1129	15.4870	4.6954
68	wallee	woman	N	16	0.0006	67.5	5	0.4280	0.0819	12.2122	2.2392
69	mífvaji	secret	N	16	0.0006	67.5	2	0.5603	0.1760	13.5083	3.6050
70	toocu -i -vbe	be_rotten -FUT -M.SG	V	16	0.0006	67.5	1	0.5764	0.1868	16.9228	7.2826
71	tsaa -ne	come -INAN	V	15	0.0005	73.0	8	0.3427	0.0941	19.6152	4.8524
72	cújuwa	fire	N	15	0.0005	73.0	7	0.5568	0.1782	12.2139	4.5353
73	llif -j	son -VOC	N	15	0.0005	73.0	7	0.2635	0.0613	23.9153	5.4638
74	i- ujcu -ne	3- take -INAN	V	15	0.0005	73.0	6	0.4896	0.1035	14.9408	3.3124
75	élle -vu -juco	there -ALL -AFIR	N	15	0.0005	73.0	5	0.3770	0.1123	28.6431	8.7242
76	imlle	want	V	14	0.0005	79.5	9	0.3903	0.1125	19.2371	16.5022
77	wajtsi	arrive	V	14	0.0005	79.5	9	0.4126	0.1195	15.7922	5.1045
78	múnaa -pi	people -CLF.man	N	14	0.0005	79.5	8	0.5561	0.1661	15.7714	5.2331
79	cááni	father	N	14	0.0005	79.5	7	0.3870	0.0915	13.6469	3.4214
80	naanú	uncle	N	14	0.0005	79.5	4	0.3674	0.1120	15.9557	4.6675
81	íínu -heju -ne	earth -CLF.hole -PL	N	14	0.0005	79.5	3	0.7559	0.2809	14.6309	4.7666
82	piíne -eme -ne	center -like -INAN	N	14	0.0005	79.5	1	0.6251	0.0794	16.2539	2.2155
83	ihchú -ba -j	heron -CLF.object -POSS	N	14	0.0005	79.5	1	0.5537	0.1358	15.2240	3.5109
84	mewa -ke	wife -ACC	N	13	0.0005	87.5	11	0.4632	0.1261	15.9312	6.4333
85	waajácu	know	V	13	0.0005	87.5	9	0.5295	0.1418	13.5541	3.2150

Table 2: The 100 most frequent word types in Bora (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	nee -híjcyá	say -REP	V	13	0.0005	87.5	9	0.4369	0.1332	19.8473	5.6106
87	nívuwa	deer	N	13	0.0005	87.5	6	0.6147	0.1550	12.0003	2.7618
88	i- doo -ne	3- eat_meat -INAN	V	13	0.0005	87.5	4	0.4490	0.0850	16.1100	3.0090
89	daállí	sloth	N	13	0.0005	87.5	2	0.6637	0.3464	11.6762	4.4832
90	nívuwa -ji	deer -CLF.disc	N	13	0.0005	87.5	1	0.5823	0.0726	15.6737	1.9166
91	mewa -di -vu	wife -ANIM -ALL	N	13	0.0005	87.5	1	0.6325	0.0788	14.4487	1.9302
92	wákimyéí	work	N	12	0.0004	97.5	8	0.5906	0.0941	13.7685	2.5835
93	i- meenu -ne	3- do -INAN	V	12	0.0004	97.5	8	0.5115	0.1143	18.4740	4.3901
94	nee -híjcyá -vbe	say -REP -M.SG	V	12	0.0004	97.5	7	0.5117	0.2305	30.6024	29.0002
95	májcho -ne	eat -INAN	V	12	0.0004	97.5	6	0.6483	0.1200	12.7480	2.4528
96	nee -meí -vbe	say -REFL -M.SG	V	12	0.0004	97.5	6	0.6320	0.0866	14.4971	2.0629
97	íá -me	animal -PL	N	12	0.0004	97.5	5	0.3803	0.0673	10.7979	1.7281
98	oomi -vbe	return -M.SG	V	12	0.0004	97.5	4	0.5808	0.2485	16.1165	7.1541
99	dillo -vbe	ask -M.SG	V	12	0.0004	97.5	4	0.4910	0.1924	21.4166	18.1776
100	mutúle -j	sister -VOC	N	12	0.0004	97.5	3	0.4021	0.0575	17.7711	2.7930

Table 3: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	meī	thing	N	153	0.0041	1.0	27	0.3605	0.1801	10.6584	5.9124
2	maʔmi	man	N	116	0.0031	2.0	20	0.3450	0.1082	15.8424	4.7728
3	numd -ma	do -INF	V	111	0.0029	3.0	17	0.3031	0.1082	18.4031	5.9065
4	ebhokad	avocado	N	100	0.0027	4.0	8	0.4250	0.1067	17.1443	4.0763
5	bakhra	goat	N	73	0.0019	5.0	18	0.3718	0.1087	17.5566	5.1751
6	u- topi	3sPOSS- cap	N	71	0.0019	6.0	16	0.3472	0.1015	15.5930	4.4588
7	cha -ce	child -ns	N	62	0.0016	7.0	16	0.3968	0.1395	14.1842	4.6816
8	cha	child	N	52	0.0014	8.0	16	0.2707	0.1043	12.9863	5.1538
9	khat -e	go -IND.PST	V	51	0.0014	9.0	16	0.3110	0.1458	19.7013	7.6696
10	seu	apple	N	50	0.0013	10.0	5	0.2967	0.1681	13.6239	5.8608
11	ma	girl	N	48	0.0013	11.5	11	0.2811	0.0998	8.1933	3.6755
12	maʔmi -ce	man -ns	N	48	0.0013	11.5	10	0.5500	0.1894	14.1221	4.3382
13	thaū	place	N	45	0.0012	13.0	11	0.2386	0.1535	24.4514	21.1165
14	ta -e	come -IND.PST	V	42	0.0011	14.0	12	0.2983	0.1370	14.7397	7.2080
15	khat -ma	go -INF	V	41	0.0011	16.0	13	0.3455	0.0991	21.8963	6.6071
16	kam -a	work -NTVZ	N	41	0.0011	16.0	12	0.3158	0.1263	14.6895	6.0465
17	bhale	cock	N	41	0.0011	16.0	9	0.3767	0.1315	14.5986	4.1997
18	thams -e	fall -IND.PST	V	39	0.0010	18.0	10	0.4335	0.1399	15.1437	4.3092
19	saikal	bicycle	N	37	0.0010	19.5	13	0.3798	0.1440	17.1756	4.3103
20	saikal -be?	bicycle -LOC	N	37	0.0010	19.5	13	0.4858	0.1122	17.8092	4.3204
21	cekt -ma	speak -INF	V	31	0.0008	21.0	13	0.3776	0.1189	14.4891	4.3294
22	u- khat -e	3nsS/A- go -IND.PST	V	30	0.0008	22.0	7	0.3327	0.0913	20.6182	5.5327
23	khind -saŋa	pull -CVB	V	29	0.0008	23.5	10	0.4219	0.1264	17.7404	5.8255
24	āba	mango	N	29	0.0008	23.5	6	0.3749	0.1525	9.4811	5.1754
25	barsa	year	N	28	0.0007	26.0	10	0.3104	0.1411	19.1541	7.7591
26	nips -a -yakt -e	look.like -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	28	0.0007	26.0	7	0.4977	0.1804	17.4397	4.3648
27	heŋga	bamboo.basket	N	28	0.0007	26.0	5	0.3155	0.1327	19.2649	7.4866
28	suyuppa	whistle	N	27	0.0007	28.5	11	0.3051	0.1031	23.6704	7.9905
29	u- cha	3sPOSS- child	N	27	0.0007	28.5	7	0.3033	0.1361	20.2313	12.6291
30	topi	cap	N	26	0.0007	30.5	7	0.2626	0.0646	16.3097	4.7600
31	philim	film	N	26	0.0007	30.5	5	0.3417	0.1291	19.4624	5.9205
32	khāŋ -ma	see -INF	V	25	0.0007	34.0	14	0.3324	0.1171	20.0383	6.4126
33	pa	boy	N	25	0.0007	34.0	10	0.2367	0.1216	12.1563	9.0253
34	u- saikal	3sPOSS- bicycle	N	25	0.0007	34.0	9	0.4018	0.0877	18.0216	3.4724
35	haknuwa	heat	N	25	0.0007	34.0	3	0.4706	0.1213	15.7962	3.8119
36	pauro	landslide	N	25	0.0007	34.0	1	0.3694	0.1423	17.5751	6.4064
37	khatt -e	take -IND.PST	V	24	0.0006	37.5	10	0.4033	0.1494	16.9307	5.7845
38	putt -u -kv	pluck -3P -IND.NPST	V	24	0.0006	37.5	4	0.4890	0.2102	15.9783	4.5989
39	putt -a -yakt -e	pick -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	23	0.0006	39.0	4	0.3765	0.0677	20.7567	4.1662
40	cha -ŋa	child -ERG.A	N	22	0.0006	40.0	7	0.4040	0.1495	13.8323	5.6251
41	katha	story	N	21	0.0006	42.5	12	0.3062	0.1491	19.4015	8.0921
42	numd -saŋa	do -CVB	V	21	0.0006	42.5	11	0.3727	0.1188	20.2787	6.8859
43	khat -no	go -IND.NPST	V	21	0.0006	42.5	9	0.4152	0.2627	19.0901	8.8595

Table 3: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	thap -no	come.across -IND.NPST	V	21	0.0006	42.5	6	0.2968	0.1302	38.2327	77.4014
45	u- khat -no	3nsS/A- go -IND.NPST	V	20	0.0005	48.0	11	0.4651	0.2337	18.3464	7.8815
46	budha	old.man	N	20	0.0005	48.0	11	0.2872	0.1279	18.3800	6.9312
47	sahayog	help	N	20	0.0005	48.0	7	0.4037	0.1145	18.5658	4.6556
48	mai- cekt -ma	NEG- speak -INF	V	20	0.0005	48.0	7	0.4970	0.1798	17.1082	5.3334
49	khatt -u -kv	take -3P -IND.NPST	V	20	0.0005	48.0	7	0.4624	0.1712	19.2512	5.9646
50	teī	village	N	20	0.0005	48.0	6	0.2936	0.0929	11.0354	2.7981
51	rupaiya	rupee	N	20	0.0005	48.0	4	0.3681	0.1574	15.7724	7.1168
52	u- meī	3sPOSS- thing	N	19	0.0005	56.0	12	0.3905	0.2191	12.7635	5.6282
53	cekt -ma	say -INF	V	19	0.0005	56.0	11	0.2913	0.0936	18.8453	5.9138
54	meī -be?	thing -LOC	N	19	0.0005	56.0	11	0.4920	0.1842	12.2444	4.6509
55	ma?mi -ja	man -ERG.A	N	19	0.0005	56.0	9	0.4447	0.1528	17.1337	4.9971
56	ca -saṅa	eat -CVB	V	19	0.0005	56.0	8	0.3555	0.1141	17.9842	10.7305
57	pakku	uncle	N	19	0.0005	56.0	5	0.3689	0.2300	16.4541	6.1825
58	cekt -saṅa	speak -CVB	V	19	0.0005	56.0	5	0.5279	0.1294	13.8210	3.5885
59	lik -e	go.up -IND.PST	V	19	0.0005	56.0	5	0.2942	0.0968	15.1619	4.8596
60	phidaṅ	ginger	N	19	0.0005	56.0	2	0.4189	0.2910	18.0626	6.5122
61	ma?mi	person	N	18	0.0005	64.0	10	0.3485	0.1134	15.7762	4.8432
62	bela	time	N	18	0.0005	64.0	7	0.2489	0.1022	18.1701	5.9716
63	putt -saṅa	pluck -CVB	V	18	0.0005	64.0	7	0.4931	0.1895	13.5778	4.9969
64	thippa	grandfather	N	18	0.0005	64.0	5	0.3762	0.1953	19.2269	7.3450
65	jangal -a	forest -NTVZ	N	18	0.0005	64.0	4	0.4823	0.0965	15.0120	2.7437
66	wat -a -ṅs -e	wear -PST -PRF -IND.PST	V	18	0.0005	64.0	3	0.5179	0.1538	14.6508	4.2438
67	ka- khutt -pa	ACT.PTCP- steal -M	V	18	0.0005	64.0	3	0.4656	0.0929	19.8416	3.4888
68	thap -e	come.across -IND.PST	V	17	0.0005	72.0	9	0.3898	0.1914	16.3089	7.9151
69	lis -e	happen -IND.PST	V	17	0.0005	72.0	7	0.2816	0.1054	16.0495	4.3497
70	pid -e	give -IND.PST	V	17	0.0005	72.0	7	0.3126	0.0766	14.8571	3.7451
71	pad -e	study -V.NTVZ	V	17	0.0005	72.0	6	0.2888	0.0780	16.4794	5.7946
72	keta -ce	boy -ns	N	17	0.0005	72.0	6	0.4302	0.1628	15.4514	4.5127
73	thams -no	fall -IND.NPST	V	17	0.0005	72.0	5	0.4671	0.1103	13.8466	3.4736
74	putt -u -kv -ta	pluck -3P -IND.NPST -IPFV	V	17	0.0005	72.0	4	0.5624	0.1266	17.0814	3.2239
75	wat -a -yakt -e	wear -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	17	0.0005	72.0	3	0.4394	0.1297	17.2728	5.0134
76	yuj -si	stay -PURP	V	17	0.0005	72.0	1	0.3224	0.2082	19.2132	7.2319
77	saikal -wala	bicycle -AGT	N	16	0.0004	79.5	7	0.5305	0.0786	19.1623	3.1150
78	mechacha	girl	N	16	0.0004	79.5	6	0.4358	0.1408	19.6256	6.0013
79	putt -no	pluck -IND.NPST	V	16	0.0004	79.5	6	0.2596	0.0609	20.7203	4.6984
80	pa	man	N	16	0.0004	79.5	6	0.1894	0.0817	13.4453	7.9732
81	ka- putt -pa	ACT.PTCP- pluck -M	V	16	0.0004	79.5	4	0.4875	0.0847	16.8721	2.8658
82	kibha	tiger	N	16	0.0004	79.5	3	0.4902	0.2714	12.5711	5.1375
83	ta	come	V	15	0.0004	87.0	8	0.1880	0.1076	13.9791	6.3968
84	paisa	money	N	15	0.0004	87.0	8	0.4125	0.1768	14.9079	7.4832
85	thakiloṅ	ladder	N	15	0.0004	87.0	6	0.5691	0.2053	16.8961	5.8990

Table 3: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	cama	food	N	15	0.0004	87.0	5	0.3411	0.1167	13.2739	4.8464
87	u- catt -e	3nsS/A- strike -IND.PST	V	15	0.0004	87.0	5	0.3247	0.0751	19.4792	3.8385
88	putt -e	pluck -IND.PST	V	15	0.0004	87.0	4	0.3764	0.1765	15.5178	5.4886
89	eksident	accident	N	15	0.0004	87.0	4	0.4248	0.0801	17.8893	3.9218
90	khatt -u -yakt -e	take -3P -IPFV -IND.PST	V	15	0.0004	87.0	4	0.5634	0.1434	20.5453	5.9642
91	bela -be?	time -LOC	N	15	0.0004	87.0	2	0.4160	0.0990	15.3107	4.1465
92	u- ta -no	3nsS/A- come -IND.NPST	V	14	0.0004	98.0	9	0.4054	0.1509	14.4729	6.1623
93	cuwa	water	N	14	0.0004	98.0	8	0.3007	0.1663	16.5597	6.7245
94	ghari	moment	N	14	0.0004	98.0	8	0.3042	0.1395	18.9182	10.7892
95	thaü -be?	place -LOC	N	14	0.0004	98.0	7	0.3353	0.0997	20.1123	6.7803
96	numd -no	do -IND.NPST	V	14	0.0004	98.0	7	0.3336	0.1154	18.0957	8.7566
97	putt -si	pluck -PURP	V	14	0.0004	98.0	6	0.2959	0.0981	17.9530	5.1318
98	cham	song	N	14	0.0004	98.0	5	0.2859	0.1470	16.4155	5.9867
99	dhakiya -be?	small.basket -LOC	N	14	0.0004	98.0	5	0.5500	0.1457	17.0085	3.9846
100	ka- putt -pa	ACT.PTCP- pick -REF	V	14	0.0004	98.0	4	0.4093	0.0439	19.7552	2.1120

Table 4: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang (no pear stories)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	numd -ma	do -INF	V	97	0.0026	1.0	12	0.3037	0.1094	18.3975	5.9790
2	mei	thing	N	43	0.0011	2.0	6	0.3894	0.1597	9.9682	6.9591
3	khat -ma	go -INF	V	40	0.0011	3.5	12	0.3444	0.1001	21.9950	6.6605
4	thaū	place	N	40	0.0011	3.5	7	0.2212	0.1386	25.6278	21.8987
5	kam -a	work -NTVZ	N	30	0.0008	5.0	6	0.3034	0.1030	14.9905	6.2766
6	païro	landslide	N	25	0.0007	6.0	1	0.3694	0.1423	17.5751	6.4064
7	maʔmi -ce	man -ns	N	24	0.0006	7.0	5	0.6594	0.1895	11.4988	3.2986
8	cekt -ma	speak -INF	V	23	0.0006	8.0	9	0.3599	0.0958	14.8324	3.8283
9	cha -ce	child -ns	N	21	0.0006	9.0	4	0.4705	0.1530	12.0886	4.1617
10	barsa	year	N	20	0.0005	10.0	7	0.3155	0.1397	18.5638	7.2560
11	teī	village	N	19	0.0005	11.5	5	0.2990	0.0921	10.7852	2.6348
12	phidaŋ	ginger	N	19	0.0005	11.5	2	0.4189	0.2910	18.0626	6.5122
13	cekt -saŋa	speak -CVB	V	18	0.0005	13.0	4	0.5334	0.1309	13.9428	3.6519
14	rupaiya	rupee	N	17	0.0005	14.5	3	0.3765	0.1567	15.7316	6.9544
15	yuŋ -si	stay -PURP	V	17	0.0005	14.5	1	0.3224	0.2082	19.2132	7.2319
16	ta -e	come -IND.PST	V	16	0.0004	16.5	5	0.3131	0.1575	14.5209	6.3652
17	kibha	tiger	N	16	0.0004	16.5	3	0.4902	0.2714	12.5711	5.1375
18	cha	child	N	15	0.0004	18.0	6	0.2513	0.1026	13.6374	4.7516
19	cekt -ma	say -INF	V	14	0.0004	20.5	7	0.2868	0.0932	19.1493	6.1380
20	cama	food	N	14	0.0004	20.5	4	0.3548	0.1080	12.3172	3.2421
21	wathī	hen's.egg	N	14	0.0004	20.5	3	0.3629	0.1119	15.4138	6.3913
22	cind -ma	teach -INF	V	14	0.0004	20.5	1	0.3493	0.1396	12.7931	3.9018
23	maʔmi	man	N	13	0.0003	26.5	7	0.3885	0.1340	14.1824	4.4095
24	katha	story	N	13	0.0003	26.5	6	0.3365	0.1766	18.1795	8.2556
25	thippa	grandfather	N	13	0.0003	26.5	3	0.4025	0.2235	18.8395	8.3093
26	mitt -ŋa -ʔa	think -1s/P -IND.NPST	V	13	0.0003	26.5	3	0.3847	0.0749	16.2594	2.8329
27	pad -e	study -V.NTVZ	V	13	0.0003	26.5	3	0.2800	0.0696	17.3309	6.0446
28	pakku	uncle	N	13	0.0003	26.5	2	0.3941	0.2731	16.2923	7.0120
29	a- phuwa	1sPOSS- cousin	N	13	0.0003	26.5	1	0.4499	0.1733	11.6496	3.6307
30	wat -a -yakt -e	wear -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	13	0.0003	26.5	1	0.4407	0.1426	17.4243	5.3470
31	ghari	moment	N	12	0.0003	34.0	6	0.3016	0.1306	18.2617	10.2090
32	teī -peʔ	village -LOC	N	12	0.0003	34.0	6	0.5092	0.1843	12.1663	6.4489
33	riŋ	matter	N	12	0.0003	34.0	4	0.2292	0.1311	16.2888	7.3220
34	cekt -e	speak -PST	V	12	0.0003	34.0	3	0.3440	0.0826	15.3826	4.0414
35	rek	anger	N	12	0.0003	34.0	2	0.2108	0.1040	16.5164	5.4087
36	chapkama	fate	N	12	0.0003	34.0	1	0.5192	0.2186	17.5227	5.8981
37	roktham	prevention	N	12	0.0003	34.0	1	0.4683	0.1397	16.1542	5.4656
38	kam -ce	friend -ns	N	11	0.0003	43.0	6	0.4411	0.1461	14.9200	4.7343
39	maʔmi	person	N	11	0.0003	43.0	4	0.2960	0.0708	17.7441	4.0281
40	thippa -ce	grandfather -ns	N	11	0.0003	43.0	4	0.5316	0.1616	16.5524	5.6193
41	haŋ	king	N	11	0.0003	43.0	4	0.3345	0.1664	11.3091	5.4167
42	khat -i	go -1/2pS/P	V	11	0.0003	43.0	3	0.2464	0.0727	21.5174	4.7818
43	a- phuwa	1sPOSS- elder.brother	N	11	0.0003	43.0	2	0.3449	0.1319	13.8278	3.8863

Table 4: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang (no pear stories) (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	makai	maize	N	11	0.0003	43.0	2	0.4598	0.2210	15.6822	7.2365
45	sahayog	help	N	11	0.0003	43.0	2	0.4445	0.1302	17.0502	4.9842
46	devi	goddess	N	11	0.0003	43.0	2	0.2764	0.0933	15.6918	4.0658
47	khahare	landslide	N	11	0.0003	43.0	1	0.4645	0.2248	16.6339	7.1518
48	numd -i -ne	do -1/2pS/P -OPT	V	11	0.0003	43.0	1	0.4344	0.1406	17.7561	6.2412
49	nambar	number	N	10	0.0003	52.0	5	0.3238	0.0769	17.4775	5.6702
50	cuwa	water	N	10	0.0003	52.0	5	0.3030	0.1451	15.6634	5.9895
51	bela	time	N	10	0.0003	52.0	5	0.2930	0.1136	15.2268	4.7507
52	doṅdum	talk	N	10	0.0003	52.0	3	0.4319	0.2300	16.4084	5.8989
53	sal -pe?	year -LOC	N	10	0.0003	52.0	2	0.3010	0.0671	17.4828	4.3925
54	bhai	brother	N	10	0.0003	52.0	2	0.3518	0.1780	14.7592	9.0404
55	jarnel	general	N	10	0.0003	52.0	1	0.5235	0.1566	12.4101	3.6871
56	paisa	money	N	9	0.0002	65.0	6	0.3476	0.1357	16.4575	6.1483
57	khaṅ -ma	see -INF	V	9	0.0002	65.0	5	0.3744	0.1530	18.2076	5.8807
58	numd -i	do -1/2pS/P	V	9	0.0002	65.0	4	0.3040	0.0634	17.2418	4.3554
59	thaū -be?	place -LOC	N	9	0.0002	65.0	4	0.3171	0.1055	21.3602	7.4507
60	kok	rice	N	9	0.0002	65.0	4	0.2618	0.1140	13.6960	6.8698
61	maṅ	deity	N	9	0.0002	65.0	4	0.2622	0.1099	14.2162	8.2938
62	dina	day	N	9	0.0002	65.0	4	0.3794	0.1075	11.5273	4.1484
63	kher	time	N	9	0.0002	65.0	3	0.1901	0.0480	27.5278	5.6481
64	cekt -ṅa -ʔa	say -1sS/P -IND.NPST	V	9	0.0002	65.0	3	0.3478	0.1026	19.2009	5.1519
65	teī -pe? -ko	village -LOC -GEN	N	9	0.0002	65.0	3	0.6340	0.1983	11.9232	3.3418
66	jaṅgal -a	forest -N.NTVZ	N	9	0.0002	65.0	3	0.5126	0.2234	15.7250	5.9504
67	khat -e	go -PST	V	9	0.0002	65.0	3	0.2858	0.0442	17.8347	2.4838
68	u- cekt -no	3nsS/A- say -IND.NPST	V	9	0.0002	65.0	2	0.3533	0.1068	18.2446	4.8693
69	gaph -a	chat -NTVZ	N	9	0.0002	65.0	2	0.2878	0.0963	18.8412	5.0218
70	phultuṅ	underwear	N	9	0.0002	65.0	1	0.5667	0.3524	15.5786	6.2344
71	ani- thippa -ce	1piPOSS- grandfather -ns	N	9	0.0002	65.0	1	0.6229	0.1857	19.1663	5.9578
72	u- sat -u -yakt -e	3nsS/A- pull.out -3P -IPFV -IND.PST	V	9	0.0002	65.0	1	0.6689	0.2709	14.0788	5.2750
73	thurum	mouth	N	9	0.0002	65.0	1	0.3039	0.2003	25.2754	10.8281
74	sikchya	education	N	9	0.0002	65.0	1	0.3934	0.1218	19.4652	6.5037
75	maʔmi -ce	person -ns	N	8	0.0002	82.0	4	0.6125	0.2058	12.4901	3.6757
76	sontoloṅ	orange	N	8	0.0002	82.0	3	0.5244	0.1884	16.6649	6.6161
77	mett -ma	do.with/to -INF	V	8	0.0002	82.0	3	0.4562	0.2916	16.6414	6.5045
78	bihe	marriage	N	8	0.0002	82.0	3	0.2112	0.0574	21.8775	5.5078
79	u- cekt -a -yakt -e	3nsS/A- say -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	8	0.0002	82.0	3	0.5481	0.1231	16.9479	3.9956
80	calan	custom	N	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.3362	0.1119	16.1766	4.8112
81	hand -ma	talk -INF	V	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.3487	0.1043	15.2218	3.6066
82	mitt -i	think -1/2pS/P	V	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.2800	0.0537	18.4455	3.5582
83	duwacha	boy	N	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.4625	0.1405	16.3210	4.7215
84	u- niṅ	3sPOSS- name	N	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.2692	0.0723	15.5418	2.9760
85	niṅ	name	N	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.1525	0.0696	23.1196	9.0113

Table 4: The 100 most frequent word types in Chintang (no pear stories) (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	helawa -ce	monkey -ns	N	8	0.0002	82.0	2	0.4750	0.1584	18.4543	5.7565
87	khur -a -hatt -e	carry.away -PST -CMPL.TR -IND.PST	V	8	0.0002	82.0	1	0.3596	0.0895	23.4223	5.5298
88	dih	small.shed	N	8	0.0002	82.0	1	0.2637	0.0713	16.1091	4.0558
89	pid -a -ŋ -a -na	give -IMP -1s/P -IMP -INSIST	V	8	0.0002	82.0	1	0.5955	0.2744	23.1956	26.2221
90	a- niŋ	1sPOSS- name	N	7	0.0002	103.5	5	0.4926	0.1265	8.7165	2.7955
91	dini	day	N	7	0.0002	103.5	5	0.2957	0.1011	14.8847	4.8836
92	ca -ma	eat -INF	V	7	0.0002	103.5	4	0.2894	0.0716	14.5594	3.6238
93	u- cekt -no	3nsS/A- speak -NPST	V	7	0.0002	103.5	4	0.5329	0.1499	12.1459	3.8054
94	ta -e	come -PST	V	7	0.0002	103.5	4	0.2970	0.1468	13.2399	9.2161
95	nam	sun	N	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.3000	0.1204	11.1820	3.5291
96	com	type	N	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.1557	0.0199	19.5521	2.6229
97	khat	go	V	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.1950	0.0497	27.3510	7.9409
98	maŋ	prayer	N	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.3029	0.1443	13.0103	9.2748
99	thau -pe?	place -LOC	N	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.4643	0.1696	15.9148	6.8510
100	khet -ma	buy -INF	V	7	0.0002	103.5	3	0.3774	0.1471	22.1208	12.9300

Table 5: The 100 most frequent word types in Dutch

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	weet	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	147	0.0037	1.0	17	0.1652	0.0563	27.2182	10.0410
2	denk	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	114	0.0029	2.0	16	0.2012	0.0532	21.4144	6.5242
3	vind	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	112	0.0028	3.0	15	0.1736	0.0549	25.6970	10.3534
4	keer	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	73	0.0019	4.0	16	0.1935	0.0835	25.4533	13.9018
5	beetje	N(soort,ev,dim,onz,stan)	N	68	0.0017	5.5	16	0.3038	0.1304	21.8623	5.8108
6	jaar	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	68	0.0017	5.5	12	0.2169	0.0874	21.6880	9.5216
7	gaat	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	66	0.0017	7.0	16	0.2170	0.0825	20.8907	7.4372
8	zeg	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	58	0.0015	8.0	12	0.1839	0.0566	18.2741	8.8001
9	gaan	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	57	0.0014	9.0	13	0.1808	0.0607	25.5154	13.3195
10	ga	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	56	0.0014	10.0	13	0.1393	0.0434	15.8754	5.3086
11	mensen	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	53	0.0013	11.0	13	0.3232	0.0931	19.9564	5.5940
12	zit	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	52	0.0013	12.0	17	0.1961	0.0824	17.7451	7.2723
13	gaan	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	51	0.0013	13.5	17	0.1935	0.0851	24.2832	9.8285
14	kinderen	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	51	0.0013	13.5	5	0.3989	0.1246	21.5033	5.1547
15	komt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	47	0.0012	15.0	16	0.2227	0.0664	19.3733	5.3033
16	ging	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	43	0.0011	16.5	12	0.2008	0.0597	21.4797	6.3730
17	bedoel	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	43	0.0011	16.5	12	0.2431	0.0999	31.9686	28.7972
18	staat	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	39	0.0010	18.0	11	0.2907	0.1090	20.1084	9.1884
19	uur	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	36	0.0009	19.5	13	0.1950	0.0978	20.8861	15.3504
20	zei	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	36	0.0009	19.5	12	0.1734	0.0533	18.8814	5.6922
21	zeggen	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	35	0.0009	21.5	16	0.2783	0.0660	22.9608	6.6164
22	dag	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	35	0.0009	21.5	13	0.2602	0.0872	12.6498	3.7301
23	tijd	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	34	0.0009	23.5	13	0.2521	0.0916	17.8673	6.2940
24	dacht	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	34	0.0009	23.5	12	0.1968	0.0444	26.7319	6.1806
25	maken	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	33	0.0008	25.0	12	0.3653	0.1095	14.9623	5.0103
26	dingen	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	32	0.0008	26.0	13	0.2503	0.0773	25.8736	7.0139
27	week	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	31	0.0008	27.0	13	0.2222	0.0662	19.8869	7.0619
28	school	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	30	0.0008	28.0	6	0.3319	0.0925	19.1587	4.2595
29	zegt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	29	0.0007	29.0	9	0.2111	0.0637	20.1673	4.5630
30	moment	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	28	0.0007	30.0	8	0.2667	0.1293	27.8153	12.6091
31	nederlands	N(eigen,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	27	0.0007	31.0	5	0.4906	0.1045	21.1805	3.9713
32	kijken	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	25	0.0006	32.0	9	0.3653	0.1135	17.9109	5.2284
33	vond	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	24	0.0006	33.5	8	0.2162	0.1116	20.5668	4.8313
34	krijg	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	24	0.0006	33.5	8	0.2405	0.0625	22.3747	6.6923
35	zie	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	23	0.0006	36.0	9	0.1555	0.0571	21.4646	6.4223
36	ligt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	23	0.0006	36.0	8	0.2391	0.1423	20.1303	8.7869
37	kijk	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	23	0.0006	36.0	8	0.2137	0.0591	20.0555	5.3537
38	staan	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	22	0.0006	39.0	14	0.3579	0.0868	14.8033	3.7028
39	gingen	WW(pv,verl,mv)	V	22	0.0006	39.0	9	0.2112	0.0559	30.1040	7.0773
40	zitten	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	22	0.0006	39.0	6	0.2709	0.0648	23.6438	6.9178
41	stukje	N(soort,ev,dim,onz,stan)	N	21	0.0005	42.0	8	0.3590	0.0765	17.4015	3.4853
42	gulden	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	21	0.0005	42.0	5	0.3060	0.0820	21.1078	6.1283
43	zon	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	21	0.0005	42.0	2	0.2565	0.0402	11.9545	1.7570

Table 5: The 100 most frequent word types in Dutch (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	zitten	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	20	0.0005	45.0	12	0.2709	0.0727	23.5184	5.6806
45	stond	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	20	0.0005	45.0	11	0.2628	0.0937	20.8833	5.7863
46	paar	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	20	0.0005	45.0	10	0.1958	0.0501	21.6962	5.4002
47	kwam	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	19	0.0005	48.0	10	0.2339	0.0595	18.1627	4.5841
48	dagen	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	19	0.0005	48.0	7	0.3240	0.0779	16.1636	3.3024
49	zat	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	19	0.0005	48.0	7	0.1800	0.0480	17.9265	5.3341
50	leerlingen	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	18	0.0005	50.0	4	0.4318	0.0957	24.3346	5.7278
51	merk	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	17	0.0004	51.5	7	0.2596	0.0629	16.3331	4.1497
52	klas	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	17	0.0004	51.5	3	0.3512	0.1034	12.3044	3.4123
53	houden	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	16	0.0004	55.5	10	0.3100	0.0863	21.3296	8.5344
54	komen	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	16	0.0004	55.5	10	0.2696	0.0449	19.0141	3.0175
55	weten	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	16	0.0004	55.5	8	0.2804	0.0817	19.2546	5.3797
56	gebruiken	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	16	0.0004	55.5	8	0.4923	0.0620	18.5657	2.4239
57	nederland	N(eigen,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	16	0.0004	55.5	4	0.4884	0.1285	19.3665	4.0885
58	keuken	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	16	0.0004	55.5	3	0.2931	0.0917	22.1923	6.3954
59	huis	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	15	0.0004	62.0	9	0.2765	0.0788	15.6535	4.8503
60	maakt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	15	0.0004	62.0	8	0.2235	0.0647	24.1474	6.8960
61	werk	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	15	0.0004	62.0	6	0.2941	0.0458	13.9292	2.2839
62	vak	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	15	0.0004	62.0	4	0.2419	0.0531	12.8487	2.2398
63	lezen	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	15	0.0004	62.0	4	0.3026	0.0714	17.2846	3.5585
64	moeder	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	15	0.0004	62.0	3	0.2597	0.0488	23.7698	3.8555
65	stad	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	15	0.0004	62.0	3	0.3161	0.0998	14.1517	5.6043
66	man	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	9	0.2384	0.0756	13.9320	4.6920
67	idee	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	9	0.3044	0.0716	13.8417	3.3816
68	geven	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	14	0.0004	71.0	9	0.3298	0.0783	16.0021	3.8896
69	laten	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	14	0.0004	71.0	9	0.2645	0.0547	19.7933	4.7766
70	wist	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	14	0.0004	71.0	9	0.1819	0.0487	23.5924	7.1187
71	geloof	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	14	0.0004	71.0	8	0.2600	0.0552	24.3407	6.6978
72	begin	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	7	0.2930	0.0422	17.3809	2.3806
73	manier	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	7	0.2799	0.0770	22.8252	5.5444
74	weken	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	7	0.2867	0.0542	18.0029	3.2605
75	hou	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	14	0.0004	71.0	5	0.1556	0.0364	20.3299	5.0753
76	boeken	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	14	0.0004	71.0	4	0.3124	0.1008	20.6861	5.1179
77	lijkt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	13	0.0003	79.0	10	0.2069	0.0486	25.4224	5.8828
78	geef	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	13	0.0003	79.0	8	0.2612	0.1023	17.1276	5.2556
79	woord	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	13	0.0003	79.0	6	0.2927	0.1312	19.5419	6.7967
80	gelezen	WW(vd,vrij,zonder)	V	13	0.0003	79.0	4	0.4432	0.2140	17.7411	4.8343
81	literatuur	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	13	0.0003	79.0	3	0.6350	0.1257	16.3408	3.2989
82	kreeg	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	12	0.0003	86.0	9	0.2350	0.0838	24.5399	10.6961
83	probleem	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	12	0.0003	86.0	9	0.4457	0.0890	18.6024	3.6183
84	krijgt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	12	0.0003	86.0	9	0.3251	0.2224	23.4989	9.7721
85	geval	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	12	0.0003	86.0	8	0.3098	0.1528	21.0059	11.8691

Table 5: The 100 most frequent word types in Dutch (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	kom	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	12	0.0003	86.0	8	0.1573	0.0544	24.2370	17.6577
87	avonds	N(soort,ev,basis,gen)	N	12	0.0003	86.0	7	0.3452	0.0843	18.2386	3.9965
88	gegeven	WW(vd,prenom,zonder)	V	12	0.0003	86.0	6	0.1899	0.0608	40.6452	13.9929
89	trein	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	12	0.0003	86.0	5	0.3169	0.0643	16.3365	3.0789
90	lees	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	12	0.0003	86.0	4	0.2519	0.0733	17.0370	4.5118
91	krijgen	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	8	0.3965	0.0883	18.6155	5.0185
92	blijven	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	7	0.4355	0.0752	16.5256	2.9549
93	gemaakt	WW(vd,vrij,zonder)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	7	0.4409	0.1852	17.9551	5.8998
94	zetten	WW(inf,vrij,zonder)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	7	0.3244	0.1003	20.3474	7.0089
95	zag	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	6	0.2207	0.0740	14.9213	4.7080
96	ouders	N(soort,mv,basis)	N	11	0.0003	96.0	6	0.3653	0.1261	18.1513	5.5927
97	vader	N(soort,ev,basis,zijd,stan)	N	11	0.0003	96.0	6	0.3519	0.0967	14.9577	3.1814
98	geld	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	11	0.0003	96.0	6	0.2889	0.0719	14.6579	3.9164
99	vindt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	11	0.0003	96.0	6	0.2103	0.0572	25.4939	7.0556
100	bed	N(soort,ev,basis,onz,stan)	N	11	0.0003	96.0	2	0.2525	0.0486	12.2908	2.3483

Table 6: The 100 most frequent word types in English

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	know	know.INF	V	803	0.0143	1.0	46	0.1915	0.1006	26.9542	14.2986
2	think	think.INF	V	385	0.0069	2.0	46	0.2526	0.1031	22.1105	7.0023
3	go -ing	go -PROG	V	190	0.0034	3.5	42	0.1969	0.1027	30.2307	10.7562
4	lot	lot	N	190	0.0034	3.5	41	0.2216	0.0769	15.0400	4.9607
5	people	people	N	187	0.0033	5.0	42	0.3563	0.1004	18.2464	5.3930
6	kind	kind	N	179	0.0032	6.0	42	0.2231	0.0577	19.1075	4.8390
7	mean	mean.INF	V	157	0.0028	7.0	38	0.2043	0.0767	22.1878	7.8044
8	time	time	N	141	0.0025	8.0	41	0.3666	0.1097	11.9398	3.7643
9	thing -s	thing -PL	N	135	0.0024	9.0	37	0.3549	0.1160	18.5884	5.6646
10	go	go.INF	V	130	0.0023	10.0	39	0.1956	0.1098	12.6032	5.4050
11	guess	guess.INF	V	119	0.0021	11.0	33	0.2718	0.1023	20.7589	7.1425
12	some - thing	some - thing	N	114	0.0020	12.0	36	0.4156	0.1260	23.5797	7.2179
13	thing	thing	N	107	0.0019	13.0	38	0.2853	0.1046	19.9026	7.2195
14	school	school	N	102	0.0018	14.0	22	0.3830	0.1168	17.1782	5.3895
15	see	see.INF	V	95	0.0017	15.0	39	0.2685	0.1258	13.5352	5.9138
16	way	way	N	93	0.0017	16.0	39	0.2333	0.0943	14.8119	5.3214
17	say	say.INF	V	78	0.0014	17.0	37	0.2802	0.1406	13.5076	7.5541
18	want	want.INF	V	77	0.0014	18.0	28	0.2038	0.0853	22.3206	7.3738
19	kid -s	kid -PL	N	74	0.0013	19.0	17	0.3741	0.1128	11.7676	4.0635
20	do -ing	do -PROG	V	72	0.0013	20.0	32	0.3093	0.0922	17.6955	5.6356
21	take	take.INF	V	71	0.0013	21.5	29	0.2577	0.0666	16.5340	4.0004
22	like	like.INF	V	71	0.0013	21.5	25	0.2621	0.1023	17.2394	5.7827
23	child -ren	child -PL	N	67	0.0012	23.0	17	0.4624	0.0993	18.1031	3.9272
24	year -s	year -PL	N	66	0.0012	24.0	27	0.3570	0.1248	15.8159	5.7316
25	day	day	N	64	0.0011	25.0	21	0.2592	0.1200	13.7401	5.4902
26	year	year	N	63	0.0011	26.0	32	0.2510	0.1093	18.9530	7.9886
27	need	need.INF	V	59	0.0011	27.5	26	0.2529	0.1026	18.1647	6.7597
28	stuff	stuff	N	59	0.0011	27.5	25	0.3753	0.1126	14.4124	4.0193
29	work	work.INF	V	58	0.0010	29.0	27	0.2922	0.1033	15.1086	4.4459
30	make	make.INF	V	57	0.0010	31.0	30	0.2275	0.0759	19.1093	5.5370
31	feel	feel.INF	V	57	0.0010	31.0	27	0.2757	0.1092	15.9968	4.5245
32	say -d	say -PAST	V	57	0.0010	31.0	24	0.2340	0.0779	18.8790	5.8719
33	went	go.PAST	V	50	0.0009	33.0	23	0.2204	0.0788	19.7520	5.1000
34	problem	problem	N	49	0.0009	34.0	24	0.4815	0.1491	15.7961	4.5855
35	work	work	N	48	0.0009	35.5	22	0.3185	0.0841	13.5466	4.0043
36	home	home	N	48	0.0009	35.5	14	0.3399	0.0866	12.6071	3.4574
37	care	care	N	46	0.0008	37.0	10	0.2997	0.1146	15.2476	5.5847
38	money	money	N	44	0.0008	38.5	23	0.3498	0.1097	15.7281	4.8385
39	talk -ing	talk -PROG	V	44	0.0008	38.5	22	0.3429	0.0789	21.6067	5.4757
40	got	get.PPART	V	41	0.0007	40.0	20	0.1756	0.0558	18.5424	5.0193
41	child	child	N	40	0.0007	41.0	8	0.3948	0.1046	13.6189	3.9987
42	come	come.INF	V	39	0.0007	42.5	23	0.2328	0.0602	18.1601	4.1146
43	put	put.INF	V	39	0.0007	42.5	21	0.2298	0.0823	14.4691	4.7446

Table 6: The 100 most frequent word types in English (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	family	family	N	38	0.0007	44.0	13	0.4497	0.0865	13.8243	2.6566
45	life	life	N	36	0.0006	45.0	20	0.3511	0.0956	12.2640	3.5234
46	thought	think.PAST	V	35	0.0006	47.0	20	0.2517	0.0724	29.6627	7.1212
47	use -d	use -PAST	V	35	0.0006	47.0	19	0.2687	0.1095	16.8795	5.7284
48	house	house	N	35	0.0006	47.0	11	0.3995	0.1238	13.7033	4.1240
49	any - thing	any - thing	N	34	0.0006	50.0	20	0.4158	0.1060	20.4840	5.2048
50	pay	pay.INF	V	34	0.0006	50.0	15	0.2336	0.0975	14.8178	5.9224
51	system	system	N	34	0.0006	50.0	10	0.4921	0.1168	12.8464	3.0772
52	seem -s	seem -3sg.PRES	V	33	0.0006	52.5	17	0.2795	0.1091	19.7495	5.6337
53	use	use.INF	V	33	0.0006	52.5	10	0.2520	0.0927	13.7927	5.6284
54	look	look.INF	V	32	0.0006	54.0	15	0.2287	0.0692	18.8871	5.1954
55	have -ing	have -PROG	V	31	0.0006	55.0	26	0.3416	0.1192	18.9400	4.4647
56	course	course	N	30	0.0005	56.5	21	0.3180	0.0843	20.1725	5.2771
57	week	week	N	30	0.0005	56.5	16	0.3335	0.1209	13.7668	5.4843
58	bit	bit	N	29	0.0005	59.0	20	0.2087	0.0806	16.0228	4.9422
59	had	have.PPART	V	29	0.0005	59.0	18	0.2739	0.1219	13.0642	5.7786
60	some - body	some - body	N	29	0.0005	59.0	17	0.3823	0.0654	21.5446	3.8456
61	keep	keep.INF	V	28	0.0005	61.5	18	0.2562	0.0433	16.1248	3.3485
62	jury	jury	N	28	0.0005	61.5	2	0.3713	0.0985	11.4407	2.7243
63	let	let.INF	V	27	0.0005	63.5	18	0.1786	0.0682	19.2726	7.7134
64	live	live.INF	V	27	0.0005	63.5	15	0.2362	0.1485	22.4714	12.0503
65	point	point	N	26	0.0005	67.5	19	0.3932	0.1245	14.0062	4.5017
66	job	job	N	26	0.0005	67.5	14	0.4170	0.1033	7.5474	1.5368
67	person	person	N	26	0.0005	67.5	14	0.4245	0.1027	14.8365	3.0806
68	dollar -s	dollar -PL	N	26	0.0005	67.5	14	0.4615	0.1497	16.6244	4.9575
69	place	place	N	26	0.0005	67.5	13	0.3727	0.1192	14.6023	4.1096
70	education	education	N	26	0.0005	67.5	7	0.5784	0.1062	16.0881	3.0832
71	start	start.INF	V	25	0.0004	72.5	19	0.3562	0.0933	14.9837	3.8774
72	find	find.INF	V	25	0.0004	72.5	17	0.3175	0.1188	13.6866	3.2904
73	tell	tell.INF	V	25	0.0004	72.5	17	0.2473	0.0530	16.9390	3.8432
74	parent -s	parent -PL	N	25	0.0004	72.5	12	0.5112	0.1332	14.5693	3.6875
75	idea	idea	N	24	0.0004	76.0	12	0.4172	0.1609	10.9377	4.0575
76	school -s	school -PL	N	24	0.0004	76.0	8	0.5059	0.1495	15.1425	4.8555
77	health	health	N	24	0.0004	76.0	7	0.2928	0.0927	22.2334	6.2764
78	try -ing	try -PROG	V	23	0.0004	80.0	18	0.3048	0.1069	21.4902	5.7086
79	part	part	N	23	0.0004	80.0	18	0.2767	0.0792	15.4872	3.8901
80	work -ing	work -PROG	V	23	0.0004	80.0	17	0.4017	0.1095	18.7305	5.2468
81	well	well	N	23	0.0004	80.0	17	0.2677	0.1570	19.2729	9.1534
82	enjoy	enjoy	V	23	0.0004	80.0	7	0.4783	0.2025	11.9891	4.3273
83	type	type	N	22	0.0004	84.0	15	0.2674	0.0691	16.0520	4.6167
84	fact	fact	N	22	0.0004	84.0	14	0.2923	0.0772	14.8362	4.7211
85	took	take.PAST	V	22	0.0004	84.0	14	0.2531	0.0744	17.0204	4.4799

Table 6: The 100 most frequent word types in English (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	love	love.INF	V	21	0.0004	87.0	14	0.2837	0.1222	16.4361	6.2626
87	agree	agree.INF	V	21	0.0004	87.0	12	0.4348	0.1784	13.4726	5.4830
88	news	news	N	21	0.0004	87.0	5	0.3103	0.0931	13.9855	4.1852
89	done	do.PPART	V	20	0.0004	92.0	14	0.2634	0.0760	16.2727	4.0724
90	friend -s	friend -PL	N	20	0.0004	92.0	11	0.4200	0.1468	18.1047	4.8109
91	college	college	N	20	0.0004	92.0	10	0.4512	0.1020	16.1947	3.4140
92	son	son	N	20	0.0004	92.0	10	0.3033	0.0695	10.4139	2.5045
93	want -ed	want -PAST	V	20	0.0004	92.0	8	0.3109	0.0730	20.3521	4.8375
94	company	company	N	20	0.0004	92.0	7	0.4504	0.0880	16.1249	3.2584
95	card	card	N	20	0.0004	92.0	5	0.3259	0.0670	12.7807	2.6349
96	time -s	time -PL	N	19	0.0003	99.0	15	0.4709	0.1125	11.2029	2.6467
97	came	come.PAST	V	19	0.0003	99.0	14	0.2803	0.0623	14.9607	3.4439
98	basic -al -ly	basic -AL -LY	N	19	0.0003	99.0	12	0.5777	0.1669	16.7626	4.4868
99	try	try.INF	V	19	0.0003	99.0	12	0.2421	0.0769	13.3920	3.6980
100	understand	understand.INF	V	19	0.0003	99.0	11	0.6120	0.1660	17.6512	5.3413

Table 7: The 100 most frequent word types in Even

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	gom -niken	say -sim.cvb	V	305	0.0082	1.0	51	0.4669	0.1008	17.8892	3.7931
2	gerbe	name	N	254	0.0068	2.0	47	0.3501	0.0934	15.2005	3.6520
3	bej	man	N	160	0.0043	3.0	37	0.2553	0.0955	13.1744	4.2071
4	aman -w	father -poss.1sg	N	122	0.0033	4.0	28	0.3859	0.1196	11.3479	3.3754
5	kuŋa	child	N	111	0.0030	5.0	30	0.3331	0.1179	13.0822	3.8672
6	bej -e-l	man -ep-pl	N	93	0.0025	6.0	28	0.3503	0.1000	15.2930	3.8185
7	gom -če	say -pf.ptc	V	87	0.0023	7.0	14	0.4139	0.0790	15.0068	2.7928
8	gom -mi	say -cond.cvb	V	82	0.0022	8.0	32	0.3767	0.1146	14.5114	4.6051
9	stado -(du)le	herd.R -loc	N	78	0.0021	9.0	23	0.5693	0.1298	12.9180	2.5937
10	enen -w	mother -poss.1sg	N	67	0.0018	10.0	24	0.3897	0.1218	11.2981	3.5321
11	tor -(du)le	earth -loc	N	55	0.0015	11.5	28	0.3991	0.1017	13.5459	3.5810
12	gom -li	say -imp.2sg	V	55	0.0015	11.5	16	0.3333	0.0767	15.8704	3.8948
13	gom -r(e) -m	say -nonfut -1sg	V	52	0.0014	13.0	12	0.3413	0.0838	18.6601	4.7708
14	kuŋa -l	child -pl	N	51	0.0014	14.0	24	0.4122	0.1009	13.0072	3.1755
15	bi -dži -n(i)	be -fut -3sg	V	50	0.0013	15.0	25	0.3897	0.1017	16.3663	3.9993
16	gom -gr(e) -r	say -hab -3pl	V	49	0.0013	16.0	16	0.4680	0.1029	15.9903	3.6405
17	tor	earth	N	47	0.0013	17.0	18	0.2435	0.0628	13.2488	3.6189
18	ha: r	know -neg.cvb	V	44	0.0012	18.0	24	0.3099	0.0967	15.5365	4.3743
19	gom -n(i)	say -3sg	V	43	0.0011	19.0	16	0.3523	0.0775	17.8638	4.0779
20	asj	woman	N	41	0.0011	20.0	15	0.3316	0.1098	9.9948	3.2798
21	oŋon -w	domestic.reindeer -acc	N	40	0.0011	21.0	17	0.3774	0.1209	11.6999	3.8587
22	em -če	come -pf.ptc	V	39	0.0010	22.5	19	0.3757	0.1061	11.3338	2.6382
23	oŋoŋga	boy	N	39	0.0010	22.5	18	0.4592	0.1282	13.9871	3.6936
24	ireli -du	summer -dat	N	38	0.0010	24.0	17	0.5262	0.1651	12.4263	3.4658
25	stado	herd.R	N	37	0.0010	25.0	13	0.4309	0.1079	12.3759	3.3935
26	abaga	grandfather	N	36	0.0010	26.5	11	0.3966	0.1134	13.6470	3.8604
27	ewen	Even	N	36	0.0010	26.5	11	0.3646	0.1225	11.7912	3.3819
28	oŋon	domestic.reindeer	N	35	0.0009	28.5	16	0.3194	0.0695	13.0214	3.4078
29	abaga -w	grandfather -poss.1sg	N	35	0.0009	28.5	9	0.5264	0.1739	12.9524	3.5310
30	ewen -di -č	Even -adjr -ins	N	34	0.0009	30.0	16	0.4496	0.0942	14.0506	2.9318
31	ga -ridži	take -ant.cvb	V	33	0.0009	32.0	21	0.4398	0.1063	16.8173	3.9407
32	ja -niken	do.what -sim.cvb	V	33	0.0009	32.0	20	0.5602	0.1425	13.2159	3.7005
33	etiken	old.man	N	33	0.0009	32.0	14	0.4439	0.0928	14.5079	2.7372
34	no: -w	younger.sibling -poss.1sg	N	32	0.0009	34.0	11	0.4182	0.1327	12.9389	4.6415
35	em -ridži	come -ant.cvb	V	31	0.0008	35.5	21	0.4867	0.1084	15.1160	3.4663
36	džu:	house	N	31	0.0008	35.5	13	0.2536	0.0933	17.6314	5.8384
37	gom -gr(e) -n(i)	say -hab -3sg	V	30	0.0008	37.0	12	0.4261	0.0943	17.1659	3.5798
38	akan -w	older.brother -poss.1sg	N	29	0.0008	38.0	13	0.4397	0.1048	9.7829	2.7813
39	hiseč'in	evening	N	27	0.0007	39.5	14	0.5078	0.0953	15.4414	3.2717
40	ja -če	do.what -pf.ptc	V	27	0.0007	39.5	14	0.4314	0.0876	9.6087	1.7757
41	nyča -di -č	Russian -adjr -ins	N	26	0.0007	42.5	12	0.5018	0.0964	14.5257	2.8086
42	badžikar	morning	N	26	0.0007	42.5	11	0.4470	0.0874	17.0078	3.3070
43	ewen -sel	Even -pl	N	26	0.0007	42.5	10	0.5484	0.1737	11.8749	3.2158

Table 7: The 100 most frequent word types in Even (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	atjkan	old.woman	N	26	0.0007	42.5	9	0.4570	0.0833	13.4943	2.1247
45	boloŋi	late.autumn	N	24	0.0006	45.0	12	0.4097	0.1264	11.7230	2.8593
46	hor -ridži	go -ant.cvb	V	23	0.0006	46.5	17	0.4539	0.1062	18.4562	3.7895
47	gerbe -n(i)	name -poss.3sg	N	23	0.0006	46.5	13	0.4465	0.1062	14.3386	4.3175
48	ja -r	do.what -neg.cvb	V	22	0.0006	48.5	14	0.3404	0.1077	11.6144	2.8066
49	go:n	say	V	22	0.0006	48.5	13	0.2547	0.0626	16.7861	4.4246
50	em -ridži -l	come -ant.cvb -pl	V	21	0.0006	52.0	14	0.5552	0.1186	14.8241	3.0432
51	aman -n(i)	father -poss.3sg	N	21	0.0006	52.0	14	0.4885	0.1027	12.8006	2.6569
52	em -r(e) -n(i)	come -nonfut -3sg	V	21	0.0006	52.0	12	0.3986	0.1136	13.3636	3.1707
53	hor -li	go -imp.2sg	V	21	0.0006	52.0	11	0.3596	0.1057	15.1089	4.6942
54	hjakŋta	tree	N	21	0.0006	52.0	11	0.4289	0.1206	17.6344	5.4094
55	ineŋi -w	day -acc	N	20	0.0005	55.0	12	0.4442	0.1336	14.7412	4.5260
56	stado -du	herd.R -dat	N	19	0.0005	57.5	15	0.6012	0.1300	12.2912	2.7998
57	dolbanj	night	N	19	0.0005	57.5	9	0.4572	0.1635	13.0521	3.6488
58	ineŋi	day	N	19	0.0005	57.5	8	0.4093	0.0927	12.5700	3.1128
59	go:n -nteken	say -mult.cvb	V	19	0.0005	57.5	8	0.5564	0.1550	17.3169	4.4998
60	ođ -r(e) -n(i)	stop -nonfut -3sg	V	18	0.0005	64.5	18	0.3865	0.1303	14.1012	4.1088
61	ukčēn -dži -m	tell -fut -1sg	V	18	0.0005	64.5	15	0.5990	0.2038	16.6765	5.2158
62	dža: -l -t(i)	relative -pl -poss.1pl.in	N	18	0.0005	64.5	10	0.5255	0.1900	14.8671	4.7314
63	anjan	year	N	18	0.0005	64.5	10	0.4393	0.1327	14.8226	4.5340
64	em -dži -n(i)	come -fut -3sg	V	18	0.0005	64.5	9	0.4256	0.1191	15.0190	3.6642
65	tol -(du)le	outside -loc	N	18	0.0005	64.5	9	0.3273	0.0727	15.9618	3.3753
66	eŋin -n(i)	mother -poss.3sg	N	18	0.0005	64.5	9	0.5859	0.1219	10.6771	2.2868
67	hiŋimkin	sin	N	18	0.0005	64.5	9	0.5577	0.1255	15.0198	3.2563
68	balda -če	be.born -pf.ptc	V	18	0.0005	64.5	8	0.5262	0.1223	13.9965	3.2272
69	imanra	snow	N	18	0.0005	64.5	8	0.4807	0.1118	12.8815	3.2123
70	ŋoka -di -č	Sakha -adjr -ins	N	17	0.0005	72.5	12	0.4492	0.0907	16.2016	3.3242
71	göl -w	firewood -acc	N	17	0.0005	72.5	9	0.3192	0.0967	13.6498	4.0957
72	hor -če	go -pf.ptc	V	17	0.0005	72.5	9	0.4601	0.0976	11.3504	2.4518
73	tugenj	winter	N	17	0.0005	72.5	9	0.4642	0.1252	9.8454	2.7197
74	ujamkan	mountain.sheep	N	17	0.0005	72.5	6	0.5451	0.1248	13.4238	2.7729
75	do:mpe -(du)le	taiga -loc	N	17	0.0005	72.5	5	0.4689	0.1391	15.8796	3.6445
76	ja -ridži -l	do.what -ant.cvb -pl	V	16	0.0004	80.5	12	0.5902	0.2224	15.1362	3.7455
77	hor -e-d -niken	go -ep-prog -sim.cvb	V	16	0.0004	80.5	11	0.6480	0.1368	16.1012	3.5551
78	bej -w	man -acc	N	16	0.0004	80.5	11	0.3211	0.1158	14.0817	5.0437
79	it -ridži	see -ant.cvb	V	16	0.0004	80.5	11	0.4771	0.1531	15.8611	4.1513
80	tor -du	earth -dat	N	16	0.0004	80.5	10	0.3886	0.1018	13.7606	3.7377
81	anjan -lken	year -prop	N	16	0.0004	80.5	9	0.6486	0.1272	15.9526	2.9758
82	anjan -du	year -dat	N	16	0.0004	80.5	9	0.6916	0.1391	12.0553	2.6639
83	ŋimer	neighbour	N	16	0.0004	80.5	7	0.4716	0.1127	13.4280	3.2303
84	kuŋa -čen	child -dim	N	16	0.0004	80.5	7	0.4804	0.1064	15.2160	3.1729
85	direktor	director.R	N	16	0.0004	80.5	2	0.5921	0.0755	13.6955	1.5661

Table 7: The 100 most frequent word types in Even (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	gerbe -w	name -acc	N	15	0.0004	90.5	13	0.4132	0.0957	15.4525	3.8590
87	kun̄a -w	child -acc	N	15	0.0004	90.5	11	0.4312	0.1326	12.6269	3.8391
88	upe: -w	grandmother -poss.1sg	N	15	0.0004	90.5	9	0.4773	0.1455	12.2313	4.2205
89	hor -r	go -neg.cvb	V	15	0.0004	90.5	9	0.3511	0.0972	15.2869	4.2721
90	ńoka	Sakha	N	15	0.0004	90.5	8	0.3649	0.1309	12.3207	4.3663
91	it -r	see -neg.cvb	V	15	0.0004	90.5	8	0.3643	0.1216	12.1776	4.0658
92	upe:	grandmother	N	15	0.0004	90.5	7	0.3407	0.0926	11.9306	4.1630
93	urekč̄en	hill	N	15	0.0004	90.5	7	0.4826	0.0936	14.7184	2.8169
94	koke -če	die -pf.ptc	V	15	0.0004	90.5	7	0.4525	0.0669	13.5069	1.8266
95	ńolten	sun	N	15	0.0004	90.5	6	0.4963	0.0952	12.4925	2.3017
96	gom -d̄zi -m	say -fut -1sg	V	14	0.0004	101.0	11	0.4273	0.0837	19.4371	4.0100
97	nelkeni	early.spring	N	14	0.0004	101.0	10	0.4760	0.1045	10.9839	2.6961
98	ja -rid̄zi	do.what -ant.cvb	V	14	0.0004	101.0	10	0.4892	0.1370	15.5267	4.8273
99	kun̄a -lken	child -prop	N	14	0.0004	101.0	9	0.6209	0.1271	13.3216	2.3408
100	om̄olga -l	boy -pl	N	14	0.0004	101.0	9	0.5004	0.1093	14.5641	2.9278

Table 8: The 100 most frequent word types in Hoocak

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	wąąksik	Indian/person	N	80	0.0035	1.0	29	0.5140	0.1345	14.3653	3.2687
2	hoocak	Hoocak	N	62	0.0027	2.0	14	0.4495	0.1094	14.0503	3.0534
3	ee-ire	say-SBJ.3PL	V	57	0.0025	3.0	25	0.5194	0.1721	8.3753	2.2499
4	horođoc = ra	look.at = NMLZ	V	50	0.0022	4.0	13	0.8353	0.2941	11.8742	3.4076
5	heeną-ga	second.son-PROP	N	48	0.0021	5.0	3	0.6249	0.1538	11.9120	3.1367
6	hokiwigax	picture	N	45	0.0019	6.0	7	0.7124	0.1924	13.4882	3.4712
7	ee	say(SBJ.3SG)	V	44	0.0019	7.0	15	0.3484	0.1055	6.3520	2.1142
8	saanik	side	N	37	0.0016	9.0	9	0.4684	0.1038	13.3931	2.9123
9	maq'ı	Earthmaker	N	37	0.0016	9.0	2	0.2883	0.0552	17.9208	3.2393
10	wakanaşge-ik-ga	frog-DIM-PROP	N	37	0.0016	9.0	2	1.0161	0.1808	12.1948	2.1518
11	hi'ac	father	N	36	0.0016	11.0	13	0.3992	0.0818	13.0582	2.7633
12	wąąk	man	N	34	0.0015	12.5	15	0.3522	0.1108	12.4206	3.8822
13	hige-ire	say.to(OBJ.3SG)-SBJ.3PL	V	34	0.0015	12.5	10	0.6228	0.1093	11.5963	2.2018
14	nijkjak	child	N	33	0.0014	14.5	12	0.6176	0.1261	11.7662	2.2446
15	hire	think	V	33	0.0014	14.5	10	0.2874	0.0690	14.6220	3.1364
16	ceek	first/new	V	31	0.0013	16.5	18	0.4073	0.1363	11.2779	4.4796
17	wakacak = ra	be.holy = NMLZ	V	31	0.0013	16.5	2	0.5538	0.2028	18.8925	8.4086
18	howe	go.about	V	30	0.0013	18.0	12	0.3612	0.1513	14.0184	8.8472
19	woorak	story	N	28	0.0012	19.0	10	0.4694	0.1120	13.4506	2.9926
20	raaş	name	N	27	0.0012	20.0	9	0.3793	0.1246	11.5646	3.9354
21	naanı	mother	N	26	0.0011	21.0	10	0.3516	0.0992	14.9343	2.8365
22	nij	water	N	24	0.0010	23.5	9	0.2690	0.1233	13.7256	6.8023
23	hapahi	go.toward	V	24	0.0010	23.5	7	0.6451	0.1332	9.7477	2.3336
24	maq'ıra	Earthmaker	N	24	0.0010	23.5	6	0.7046	0.1298	10.2321	2.0568
25	mijnak = nak-šana	sit(SBJ.3SG) = POS.NTL(SBJ.3SG)-DECL	V	24	0.0010	23.5	4	0.9187	0.1593	14.5805	2.6430
26	ciı	house	N	23	0.0010	26.5	13	0.3205	0.1393	11.0153	4.3191
27	pıı	be.good	V	23	0.0010	26.5	11	0.2469	0.0815	13.6788	5.2884
28	maqıxete	white.man	N	22	0.0009	28.5	11	0.5678	0.1475	13.0721	3.1475
29	waagax = ra	paper = NMLZ	N	22	0.0009	28.5	3	0.7020	0.1172	11.6957	1.9166
30	hinuk	woman	N	21	0.0009	30.5	8	0.3865	0.0544	13.1843	1.8694
31	şuukxete	horse	N	21	0.0009	30.5	4	0.6549	0.1438	12.9878	3.2717
32	nij = ra	water = NMLZ	N	20	0.0009	33.0	9	0.4780	0.1391	11.3827	3.5209
33	maq-ija	earth-there	N	20	0.0009	33.0	6	0.5288	0.1416	11.6179	3.1408
34	şa-wagax-i-kjene	2.A-write(OBJ.3SG)-0-FUT	V	20	0.0009	33.0	4	1.1480	0.1627	11.5523	1.7102
35	roo = ra	body = NMLZ	N	19	0.0008	35.0	7	0.5016	0.2012	11.4068	4.0080
36	haap	day	N	18	0.0008	37.5	9	0.3485	0.1553	13.0566	4.0922
37	giis	be.round	V	18	0.0008	37.5	4	0.5137	0.1662	8.9005	3.4136
38	haap-hokahi	day-every	N	18	0.0008	37.5	3	0.6012	0.1805	15.8067	3.1267
39	şuuk-ik-ga	dog-DIM-PROP	N	18	0.0008	37.5	3	0.7167	0.1549	10.2786	2.1727
40	ciı-eeja	house-there	N	17	0.0007	40.5	9	0.5176	0.1492	12.6070	4.0968
41	rook-eeja	inside-there	N	17	0.0007	40.5	9	0.6234	0.1807	12.5472	3.0541
42	hi'ıni	mother	N	16	0.0007	44.0	10	0.4507	0.1196	14.1661	3.5752
43	howe	go.about(SBJ.3SG)	V	16	0.0007	44.0	8	0.3616	0.1160	12.9126	6.7456

Table 8: The 100 most frequent word types in Hooçak (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	naşsu = ra	head = NMLZ	N	16	0.0007	44.0	7	0.6193	0.1954	12.0854	2.8113
45	sijc = ra	tail = NMLZ	N	16	0.0007	44.0	6	0.6746	0.1478	9.2929	2.0009
46	saanik-eja	side-there	N	16	0.0007	44.0	4	0.7855	0.1916	12.1665	3.2207
47	hicakoro	friend	N	15	0.0006	50.5	10	0.5957	0.1776	14.9210	5.6138
48	xete	be.big	V	15	0.0006	50.5	10	0.3845	0.1558	11.8112	3.8996
49	hi < ha > re	< 1E.A > think(OBJ.3SG)	V	15	0.0006	50.5	9	0.6397	0.2150	8.6462	2.8179
50	hitek	maternal.uncle	N	15	0.0006	50.5	9	0.3736	0.0897	14.6726	6.3208
51	serec	be.long	V	15	0.0006	50.5	7	0.6099	0.2126	9.2464	3.3522
52	wani	meat	N	15	0.0006	50.5	5	0.5173	0.1765	8.8188	3.6922
53	hicawı	wife	N	15	0.0006	50.5	4	0.5095	0.1154	12.4339	3.1990
54	wakanaşge-ik	frog-DIM	N	15	0.0006	50.5	2	0.9695	0.2074	11.8109	2.3903
55	maq	earth	N	14	0.0006	61.5	9	0.2744	0.0993	12.2733	4.2425
56	waagax	paper	N	14	0.0006	61.5	9	0.5231	0.1425	12.3043	3.3667
57	gipiesge	be.enjoyable	V	14	0.0006	61.5	8	1.0144	0.5046	10.0469	4.8036
58	raaş = ra	name = NMLZ	N	14	0.0006	61.5	8	0.5966	0.1983	11.2739	4.2269
59	hoit'e = ra	language = NMLZ	N	14	0.0006	61.5	8	0.6199	0.1743	14.3798	6.0841
60	xee	hill	N	14	0.0006	61.5	8	0.3519	0.1954	9.9736	3.1126
61	ciinaq	village	N	14	0.0006	61.5	8	0.5102	0.0765	12.0409	2.0567
62	paa = ra	nose = NMLZ	N	14	0.0006	61.5	6	0.5012	0.1313	10.5936	2.5857
63	hit'e	speak	V	14	0.0006	61.5	5	0.3472	0.1300	16.2032	5.4888
64	reehi	do.quickly(SBJ.3SG)	V	14	0.0006	61.5	4	0.5417	0.1661	9.7637	2.4791
65	horoğoc = naq-şana	look.at(SBJ.3SG&OBJ.3SG) = POS.NTL(SBJ.3SG)-DECL	V	14	0.0006	61.5	4	1.1415	0.2393	12.7583	2.5847
66	ş'aak	parent	V	14	0.0006	61.5	3	0.3520	0.0804	14.8106	2.9192
67	şuqk	dog	N	14	0.0006	61.5	3	0.4404	0.1181	9.5737	2.0449
68	wakanaşge = ra	frog = NMLZ	N	14	0.0006	61.5	3	0.8971	0.1725	12.6079	1.9941
69	mijnaq	sit(SBJ.3SG)	V	13	0.0006	72.5	8	0.4842	0.1041	12.9389	2.8319
70	hi < ha > peres-nı	< 1E.A > know(OBJ.3SG)-NEG.FIN	V	13	0.0006	72.5	7	0.7998	0.1793	13.1908	3.4080
71	ee-na	say(SBJ.3SG)-DECL	V	13	0.0006	72.5	6	0.4766	0.1766	9.4771	2.3566
72	saanik-eeja	side-there	N	13	0.0006	72.5	5	0.8091	0.1425	11.2652	2.2470
73	t'aap	get.down(SBJ.3SG)	V	13	0.0006	72.5	4	0.4079	0.0730	12.5885	2.0364
74	hi-wagax-i-kjene	1LA-write(OBJ.3SG)-0-FUT	V	13	0.0006	72.5	3	1.0639	0.1468	12.4894	2.1465
75	maqşu = ra	feather = NMLZ	N	13	0.0006	72.5	2	0.7125	0.2075	10.8098	2.6929
76	nij-gi-taa	1&2-APPL.BEN-ask.for(OBJ.3SG)	V	13	0.0006	72.5	1	0.4942	0.1441	13.2945	4.4872
77	waqk = ra	man = NMLZ	N	12	0.0005	79.5	11	0.5167	0.0823	11.7261	2.0556
78	maq	year	N	12	0.0005	79.5	8	0.3660	0.2494	9.9197	3.1306
79	waqkşik = ra	Indian/person = NMLZ	N	12	0.0005	79.5	8	0.8038	0.2628	12.3002	3.9513
80	ee = naqkre	say = POS.NTL.PL:PROX	V	12	0.0005	79.5	8	0.6606	0.1278	12.3793	2.2921
81	hinik	son	N	12	0.0005	79.5	6	0.3802	0.1372	14.2998	3.6748
82	ha-hii	1E.A-arrive.there	V	12	0.0005	79.5	6	0.3932	0.1523	13.0728	8.1285
83	waruc	food	N	11	0.0005	90.5	8	0.4865	0.1651	11.3113	3.5494
84	ş'aak	be.old	V	11	0.0005	90.5	8	0.4892	0.1582	10.9835	2.6687
85	hawa'u	reason	N	11	0.0005	90.5	8	0.5875	0.0770	10.5037	1.2443

Table 8: The 100 most frequent word types in Hoocak (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	hi < hi > ge-ire	< 1E.U > say.to-SBJ.3PL	V	11	0.0005	90.5	7	0.6323	0.1865	13.5485	3.6326
87	hi < ha > peres	< 1E.A > know	V	11	0.0005	90.5	7	0.8651	0.1117	9.3895	1.2238
88	mijinaḡ-naḡa	sit(SBJ.3SG)-and	V	11	0.0005	90.5	6	0.8674	0.1628	11.9094	2.2584
89	ni-eeja	water-there	N	11	0.0005	90.5	6	0.5729	0.2966	21.3837	32.2957
90	jaaji	father	N	11	0.0005	90.5	5	0.3497	0.0417	14.4546	1.4765
91	wakanaḡḡe	frog	N	11	0.0005	90.5	3	0.8603	0.2831	11.6295	4.0971
92	waagax_haca	go.to.school\1E.A	V	11	0.0005	90.5	3	0.8200	0.1171	12.8999	2.4683
93	maḡḡḡu	feather	N	11	0.0005	90.5	3	0.5567	0.1019	11.1149	2.0597
94	waisḡap = ra	bread = NMLZ	N	11	0.0005	90.5	2	0.7510	0.2729	13.6787	5.3447
95	hoit'e = aakre	language = POS.HOR:PROX	N	11	0.0005	90.5	2	0.6381	0.1033	16.0366	2.5156
96	tuuḡa-gi	uncover(OBJ.3SG)\1E.A-TOP	V	11	0.0005	90.5	2	0.7865	0.1629	9.2405	1.8345
97	horoḡoc	look.at(SBJ.3SG&OBJ.3SG)	V	11	0.0005	90.5	2	0.5233	0.1025	13.7762	2.3020
98	waḡjik-ik-ga	rabbit-DIM-PROP	N	11	0.0005	90.5	1	0.8046	0.1880	11.7031	2.5483
99	hijaḡi	be.different	V	10	0.0004	107.5	8	0.6122	0.2140	12.4738	9.6032
100	wahe = naḡ-ḡanaḡ	talk\1E.A = POS.NTL\1E.A-DECL	V	10	0.0004	107.5	6	0.9957	0.3192	12.0520	4.3391

Table 9: The 100 most frequent word types in N|ng

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	ii	take	V	261	0.0101	1.0	27	0.2121	0.0729	15.7932	5.3135
2	ku	QUOT	V	229	0.0089	2.0	25	0.1680	0.0634	13.5126	4.8549
3	'ae	go	V	183	0.0071	3.0	26	0.2498	0.0915	18.0202	6.2603
4	'aa	go	V	173	0.0067	4.0	26	0.2465	0.1075	18.5918	6.4778
5	ki	place	N	169	0.0065	5.0	29	0.1729	0.0665	13.4965	6.1111
6	saa	come	V	144	0.0056	6.0	28	0.2488	0.0957	14.3319	6.0282
7	kx'uu	make	V	143	0.0055	7.0	23	0.2610	0.0955	21.2221	8.0859
8	see	come	V	122	0.0047	8.5	19	0.2055	0.0552	16.0072	4.0605
9	dyaqnn	walk	V	122	0.0047	8.5	16	0.2985	0.0666	21.1568	5.0272
10	!ae	run	V	116	0.0045	10.5	16	0.2358	0.0801	14.1766	4.7889
11	!'huun -si	white.person -SGLT	N	116	0.0045	10.5	15	0.3819	0.1105	22.3824	5.5837
12	g ain	brown.hyena	N	115	0.0044	12.0	5	0.2893	0.0845	18.6760	5.2711
13	soo	sit	V	105	0.0041	13.0	24	0.2415	0.0775	14.0219	3.8955
14	ain	eat	V	101	0.0039	14.0	13	0.2724	0.1011	12.4496	4.5067
15	sii	come	V	97	0.0038	16.0	24	0.2170	0.0901	15.9471	5.6901
16	!'ee	put.in	V	97	0.0038	16.0	19	0.3008	0.0953	14.5016	4.2076
17	aan	eat	V	97	0.0038	16.0	14	0.2209	0.0655	14.8348	4.6175
18	tyuin	what	N	95	0.0037	18.0	15	0.2378	0.0809	23.3942	7.9531
19	qoqon	dance	V	90	0.0035	19.0	8	0.3619	0.0749	17.2632	3.4961
20	n aa	stay	V	88	0.0034	20.0	22	0.2786	0.0953	16.0533	5.5541
21	ka	say	V	82	0.0032	21.0	22	0.1779	0.0648	13.1259	5.8830
22	!xoa	speak	V	81	0.0031	22.0	18	0.3081	0.0823	13.8811	3.5843
23	!qau	pound	V	78	0.0030	23.0	4	0.3032	0.0763	14.0624	3.7632
24	oba	child	N	76	0.0029	24.0	16	0.3199	0.0849	13.3003	3.3908
25	n aa	see	V	75	0.0029	25.5	23	0.3112	0.0912	14.0427	4.3592
26	xae -a	know -?	V	75	0.0029	25.5	20	0.3680	0.1063	14.8384	4.5976
27	ai	take	V	73	0.0028	27.0	16	0.1989	0.0700	16.8453	5.5780
28	gao	thing	N	69	0.0027	28.0	20	0.2352	0.0790	13.9777	4.3089
29	n ang	house	N	66	0.0026	29.0	19	0.3094	0.0771	17.2555	4.7265
30	g ai	be.on	V	63	0.0024	30.0	20	0.2171	0.0606	19.6841	4.8845
31	n ai	see	V	61	0.0024	31.0	16	0.2771	0.0940	16.0772	5.5432
32	!'ee	go.in	V	57	0.0022	32.0	17	0.2828	0.0906	15.3750	4.3170
33	xae	know	V	56	0.0022	33.0	16	0.3414	0.1105	13.0681	4.6570
34	hau	take.off	V	53	0.0021	34.0	16	0.2588	0.0733	17.3203	4.5039
35	!aqe	look	V	50	0.0019	35.5	18	0.3246	0.1143	13.4493	3.7213
36	!'ii	be.inside	V	50	0.0019	35.5	12	0.2190	0.0447	19.1152	4.3745
37	stui	sit.down	V	49	0.0019	38.0	21	0.3190	0.1001	14.4809	4.6108
38	'aa	go.to	V	49	0.0019	38.0	20	0.2919	0.0844	14.8107	4.1104
39	aa	give	V	49	0.0019	38.0	14	0.2010	0.0764	11.8968	5.9909
40	ii -a	take -IMP.SG	V	48	0.0019	40.5	9	0.2876	0.0832	15.1257	4.6914
41	n oon	dune	N	48	0.0019	40.5	6	0.3281	0.1060	16.7333	4.9760
42	!'huun	white.person	N	47	0.0018	42.0	12	0.3073	0.0764	20.7239	5.2011
43	!oo	man	N	46	0.0018	44.0	13	0.2360	0.0683	13.9329	4.6054

Table 9: The 100 most frequent word types in N[ng] (continued)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	n[ng]	house	N	46	0.0018	44.0	12	0.3203	0.1037	14.3759	6.9134
45	!qhaa	water	N	46	0.0018	44.0	8	0.3802	0.1103	14.3585	4.6347
46	'ang	go.and	V	45	0.0017	47.0	17	0.2369	0.0645	18.7726	5.3916
47	oe -ke	child.PL -PL	N	45	0.0017	47.0	12	0.3377	0.0850	15.6916	3.9743
48	koro	jackal	N	45	0.0017	47.0	6	0.3034	0.0757	14.0081	3.5337
49	tyoa	finish	V	43	0.0017	50.0	14	0.3307	0.0923	13.1005	4.0273
50	!'ii	fire	N	43	0.0017	50.0	12	0.2835	0.1025	15.8340	5.5359
51	hau	take.out	V	43	0.0017	50.0	10	0.2594	0.0696	17.5339	4.1530
52	kx'uu	do	V	42	0.0016	52.0	14	0.2285	0.0591	23.1010	4.9854
53	tyhaa'i	tasty	V	41	0.0016	53.0	9	0.5148	0.1207	14.3037	3.2950
54	dyisi	what	N	39	0.0015	54.5	11	0.2852	0.0909	19.3434	6.5914
55	xaan	sack	N	39	0.0015	54.5	10	0.3518	0.1041	15.5649	5.1701
56	ki	have	V	38	0.0015	58.5	17	0.1640	0.0581	13.7638	5.0434
57	xain -ki	mother -?	N	38	0.0015	58.5	11	0.4282	0.1287	15.1638	4.1642
58	hoen	elder	N	38	0.0015	58.5	9	0.2473	0.0415	20.8094	3.6727
59	‡ee	people	N	38	0.0015	58.5	8	0.2114	0.0537	15.0294	3.5305
60	⊙oe	meat	N	38	0.0015	58.5	7	0.2577	0.0757	12.8900	4.9406
61	!'aun	ground	N	38	0.0015	58.5	6	0.3005	0.0821	17.5463	3.6887
62	'ali	wash	V	37	0.0014	62.0	5	0.3458	0.0934	15.6807	4.9242
63	'aa	go.away	V	36	0.0014	65.5	15	0.2882	0.1070	15.7539	5.8283
64	uu	take.up	V	36	0.0014	65.5	15	0.1726	0.0646	13.2900	5.2173
65	'ae	go.away	V	36	0.0014	65.5	13	0.2399	0.1056	19.2499	6.3935
66	'au	dig	V	36	0.0014	65.5	7	0.3393	0.1111	12.9391	3.8746
67	ka-!kx'ora	DIST- play	V	36	0.0014	65.5	6	0.5565	0.1018	16.2622	3.5738
68	‡hee -ke	sing -?	V	36	0.0014	65.5	1	0.4064	0.0774	15.3098	3.0070
69	'ae	go.to	V	35	0.0014	69.5	12	0.2487	0.0713	17.6457	6.0090
70	ae -ki	woman -?	N	35	0.0014	69.5	8	0.4184	0.1013	12.7950	3.8512
71	n aa	see.IMP	V	34	0.0013	72.5	8	0.3131	0.0928	13.6981	3.4035
72	'ann'a	go.there	V	34	0.0013	72.5	8	0.3748	0.1084	20.1528	5.4967
73	piri	goat	N	34	0.0013	72.5	6	0.2881	0.0776	14.9025	4.1671
74	!kx'ora	play	V	34	0.0013	72.5	4	0.3904	0.0943	14.0867	3.6394
75	‡haun	pour	V	33	0.0013	75.0	14	0.2913	0.0645	17.9778	3.9254
76	‡au	tsamma	N	32	0.0012	76.0	5	0.3419	0.0755	9.2522	2.3300
77	hoo	get	V	31	0.0012	78.5	15	0.2620	0.0619	12.1126	3.0888
78	xoo	put.down	V	31	0.0012	78.5	13	0.2524	0.0700	17.1216	4.9155
79	aa -ke	berry -PL	N	31	0.0012	78.5	5	0.4062	0.0881	13.0406	3.8263
80	oa -xu	sheep -?	N	31	0.0012	78.5	4	0.4591	0.0921	11.5417	3.7526
81	‡ao	want	V	30	0.0012	82.0	11	0.2184	0.0605	14.7094	3.9351
82	quu	put.in	V	30	0.0012	82.0	6	0.2952	0.0705	14.1868	2.9085
83	suri -ke	rub.off -?	V	30	0.0012	82.0	1	0.5017	0.1731	14.8978	3.3566
84	dyee	be.how	V	29	0.0011	85.0	12	0.2223	0.0945	20.1425	7.0921
85	kx'ain	drink	V	29	0.0011	85.0	8	0.3675	0.1340	18.2439	5.8926

Table 9: The 100 most frequent word types in N[ng] (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	aa	cut	V	29	0.0011	85.0	7	0.2516	0.0814	13.3800	5.2731
87	hui	help	V	28	0.0011	88.0	12	0.3172	0.1335	11.1476	4.8482
88	tyuu	who	N	28	0.0011	88.0	10	0.1972	0.0713	22.3143	6.3184
89	n au	hare	N	28	0.0011	88.0	4	0.2901	0.1102	19.2416	5.9782
90	n aa	head	N	27	0.0010	92.5	12	0.3233	0.1219	14.2476	5.7383
91	uin	sun	N	27	0.0010	92.5	9	0.2902	0.0743	18.2662	4.3241
92	n ji	see	V	27	0.0010	92.5	5	0.3285	0.1095	13.3445	3.9941
93	xau -ke	blood -PL	N	27	0.0010	92.5	3	0.4446	0.1193	14.5476	4.3303
94	dyoo	skin	N	27	0.0010	92.5	3	0.2526	0.0834	17.1986	4.4446
95	ts'au	milk	V	27	0.0010	92.5	3	0.4156	0.1158	12.9658	3.6839
96	kiin	lie.down	V	26	0.0010	99.0	11	0.2817	0.1159	16.2783	6.0027
97	sii -a	come -IMP.SG	V	26	0.0010	99.0	11	0.3779	0.0957	11.9394	3.2063
98	kx'aan	drink	V	26	0.0010	99.0	9	0.3283	0.1368	21.0177	7.3565
99	hai -ke	milk -PL	N	26	0.0010	99.0	8	0.4367	0.1080	14.5290	3.4444
100	au	take	V	26	0.0010	99.0	7	0.1325	0.0583	17.2327	5.7998

Table 10: The 100 most frequent word types in Sakha

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	die -an	say -PF.CVB	V	409	0.0192	1.0	16	0.2424	0.0780	18.0642	5.2979
2	kihi	person	N	145	0.0068	2.0	14	0.2754	0.1164	16.6421	5.7548
3	gin -an	do -PF.CVB	V	97	0.0046	3.0	14	0.2794	0.1044	20.3700	7.3308
4	oyo	child	N	95	0.0045	4.0	14	0.2786	0.0975	12.1729	4.6864
5	bari	all	N	88	0.0041	5.0	14	0.2896	0.1087	15.2930	4.8039
6	sil	year	N	87	0.0041	6.0	14	0.2151	0.0812	15.7267	5.1308
7	kel -an	come -PF.CVB	V	75	0.0035	7.0	14	0.3534	0.0907	14.9428	3.3640
8	bar -an	go -PF.CVB	V	67	0.0031	8.0	12	0.3193	0.0763	16.5240	3.4905
9	saya -na	time -LOC	N	60	0.0028	9.0	14	0.4786	0.1679	13.6538	3.6177
10	seri:	war	N	51	0.0024	10.0	12	0.3457	0.1134	15.7718	4.5125
11	sil -la:χ -ga	year -PROP -DAT	N	49	0.0023	11.5	12	0.5985	0.2477	16.1258	4.2851
12	sür -la:χ	very.much -PROP	N	49	0.0023	11.5	11	0.4566	0.1177	16.2896	5.0741
13	aya -(i)m	father -POSS.1SG	N	48	0.0023	13.0	11	0.3795	0.0986	11.2851	3.1916
14	oyomfior	old.man	N	47	0.0022	14.0	10	0.4972	0.1595	15.3178	4.3824
15	olor -ar	sit -PRSPT	V	46	0.0022	15.0	11	0.3953	0.0758	15.7503	3.1811
16	bihir: -la:χ	appearance -PROP	N	42	0.0020	16.0	14	0.4809	0.1398	20.2643	6.8502
17	oyo -lar	child -PL	N	41	0.0019	17.0	12	0.4265	0.0894	14.7260	3.3429
18	tuoyχ -ga	what -DAT	N	40	0.0019	18.0	11	0.4594	0.1073	13.7133	2.9680
19	çon -lar	people -PL	N	39	0.0018	19.5	11	0.4301	0.0903	14.6150	3.3566
20	bari -(t)in	all -ACC.3SG	N	39	0.0018	19.5	10	0.4273	0.0623	16.7532	2.6700
21	bari -(t)a	all -POSS.3SG	N	38	0.0018	21.0	13	0.3697	0.0880	16.9545	3.3209
22	saxa	Sakha	N	37	0.0017	22.5	11	0.3258	0.1343	13.5392	3.6393
23	die -ar	say -PRSPT	V	37	0.0017	22.5	9	0.2968	0.1362	15.5468	6.3017
24	iye -(i)m	mother -POSS.1SG	N	36	0.0017	24.0	12	0.3675	0.0901	11.5936	3.0893
25	die -ar -lar	say -PRSPT -PL	V	35	0.0016	25.0	10	0.4345	0.1210	17.5367	5.7030
26	öl -an	die -PF.CVB	V	33	0.0015	26.5	10	0.2826	0.0815	15.6754	5.8363
27	bar -a	go -IPF.CVB	V	33	0.0015	26.5	7	0.2417	0.0477	17.1748	3.3781
28	oyo -la:χ	child -PROP	N	32	0.0015	28.0	10	0.5599	0.1471	13.3840	3.5533
29	ial	family	N	31	0.0015	29.5	11	0.3197	0.1489	10.9176	3.6509
30	sebieskej	Soviet.R	N	31	0.0015	29.5	7	0.5243	0.0832	17.5595	2.6284
31	sir -ga	place -DAT	N	30	0.0014	33.0	13	0.3789	0.1017	14.0326	3.3567
32	tayis -an	go.out -PF.CVB	V	30	0.0014	33.0	11	0.4125	0.0875	15.0595	2.6180
33	oloχ	life	N	30	0.0014	33.0	10	0.3230	0.0908	13.2527	3.3944
34	üle -la: -ar	work -VR -PRSPT	N	30	0.0014	33.0	8	0.4743	0.1193	15.6471	3.7991
35	taba	reindeer	N	30	0.0014	33.0	6	0.3098	0.0791	13.7203	3.4337
36	öl -bit -(t)a	die -PSTPT -POSS.3SG	V	29	0.0014	36.0	12	0.5037	0.1603	12.7467	4.5531
37	olor -a -bit	sit -IPF.CVB -1PL	V	28	0.0013	37.5	12	0.5261	0.1441	16.3181	4.3462
38	çon	people	N	28	0.0013	37.5	10	0.2358	0.0594	13.6206	3.9283
39	üle	work	N	27	0.0013	39.0	9	0.2799	0.1200	12.2289	3.6681
40	küs	girl	N	26	0.0012	41.5	10	0.3407	0.1420	13.5778	5.0602
41	böyö	multitude	N	26	0.0012	41.5	10	0.3027	0.0863	14.4025	4.6060
42	sajin	summer	N	26	0.0012	41.5	10	0.3257	0.0768	17.5889	11.9215
43	inaχ	cow	N	26	0.0012	41.5	9	0.2835	0.0675	14.7879	3.0819

Table 10: The 100 most frequent word types in Sakha (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	kihi	man	N	25	0.0012	45.0	9	0.2784	0.1118	16.4108	5.7427
45	čje	house	N	25	0.0012	45.0	9	0.2190	0.0396	14.1563	2.7112
46	uol	boy	N	25	0.0012	45.0	7	0.2921	0.0989	11.4395	3.9151
47	üle -lar -an	work -VR -PF.CVB	N	24	0.0011	47.5	9	0.4945	0.1366	15.1765	3.9794
48	kir -an	enter -PF.CVB	V	24	0.0011	47.5	8	0.3940	0.1086	16.3662	4.1640
49	olor -a -bin	sit -IPF.CVB -PRED.1SG	V	23	0.0011	50.5	10	0.5275	0.0950	15.6097	2.6336
50	sirít -an	go -PF.CVB	V	23	0.0011	50.5	9	0.3690	0.0800	16.8246	2.8593
51	kör -an	see -PF.CVB	V	23	0.0011	50.5	8	0.3619	0.1054	14.9007	4.1118
52	saɣa -li:	Sakha -ADVR	N	23	0.0011	50.5	6	0.4594	0.1003	16.0140	2.9566
53	üle -lar -a	work -lar -IPF.CVB	N	22	0.0010	53.5	9	0.3642	0.0685	17.0471	3.4383
54	oskuola -ga	school.R -DAT	N	22	0.0010	53.5	8	0.5425	0.1210	17.2492	3.2151
55	küs -(i)m	girl -POSS.1SG	N	21	0.0010	55.0	6	0.4059	0.1189	15.9508	4.5615
56	törö: -bit	be.born -PSTPT	V	20	0.0009	58.5	9	0.5237	0.0978	15.7336	2.6446
57	kihi -(n)i	person -ACC	N	20	0.0009	58.5	9	0.3563	0.1183	18.9505	7.8361
58	sana: -a -bin	think -IPF.CVB -PRED.1SG	V	20	0.0009	58.5	7	0.4937	0.0939	16.7859	3.3184
59	kihin	winter	N	20	0.0009	58.5	7	0.3876	0.1169	13.6769	2.8941
60	bar -ar	go -PRSPT	V	20	0.0009	58.5	7	0.3434	0.0698	15.1240	3.0381
61	a:t -(t)a	name -POSS.3SG	N	20	0.0009	58.5	6	0.3280	0.0823	12.9404	3.2466
62	biensije -ga	pension.R -DAT	N	19	0.0009	63.5	11	0.4879	0.0773	19.5608	3.4050
63	sirít -ar	go -PRSPT	V	19	0.0009	63.5	8	0.3742	0.0975	17.1699	5.0325
64	ontuka -(i)ŋ	this -POSS.2SG	N	19	0.0009	63.5	7	0.3863	0.1189	14.6646	4.6211
65	büt -(i)ar -an	end -CAUS -PF.CVB	V	19	0.0009	63.5	6	0.4359	0.0941	16.8583	4.1354
66	ulat -an	grow -PF.CVB	V	18	0.0008	68.0	10	0.5891	0.1329	12.5231	2.7618
67	kün	day	N	18	0.0008	68.0	9	0.1968	0.0438	15.9917	3.6877
68	die -bit	say -PSTPT	V	18	0.0008	68.0	7	0.3839	0.1347	17.3071	5.3274
69	ɣarči	money	N	18	0.0008	68.0	4	0.3806	0.0755	13.6120	2.5743
70	oɣo -lar -bit	child -PL -1PL	N	18	0.0008	68.0	3	0.6216	0.1454	15.2334	3.5563
71	böyö -(n)i	multitude -ACC	N	17	0.0008	73.5	8	0.3859	0.0829	16.3388	4.1308
72	tur -an	stand -PF.CVB	V	17	0.0008	73.5	8	0.3603	0.0794	14.6137	3.6705
73	bilas	power.R	N	17	0.0008	73.5	7	0.3656	0.0607	16.8471	2.8436
74	kuorat -ga	town.R -DAT	N	17	0.0008	73.5	5	0.4785	0.1144	17.7453	4.7981
75	eđi:j -(i)m	older.sister -POSS.1SG	N	17	0.0008	73.5	5	0.4782	0.1252	15.7039	4.5140
76	ot	hay	N	17	0.0008	73.5	5	0.2306	0.0968	10.0165	3.2841
77	kolɣos	collective.farm.R	N	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.5082	0.1391	13.1845	2.8439
78	üöreɣ -(t)a	studies -POSS.3SG	N	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.4361	0.1509	15.2797	5.2760
79	olor -an	sit -PF.CVB	V	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.4313	0.0762	14.3617	2.7804
80	sir -(t)igar	place -DAT.3SG	N	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.4416	0.1500	17.9020	7.1728
81	uol -(i)m	boy -POSS.1SG	N	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.3758	0.1282	14.5229	4.1089
82	oɣor -an	make -PF.CVB	V	16	0.0008	81.5	7	0.3886	0.0781	16.0413	3.3049
83	kolɣos -ga	collective.farm.R -DAT	N	16	0.0008	81.5	6	0.6919	0.1866	12.8967	3.3801
84	bult -sit	bag/catch -AGNR	N	16	0.0008	81.5	6	0.4482	0.1321	14.2421	3.2964
85	sit -ar	lie -PRSPT	V	16	0.0008	81.5	6	0.3423	0.0984	15.7489	4.4122

Table 10: The 100 most frequent word types in Sakha (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	üören -a	learn -IPF.CVB	V	16	0.0008	81.5	5	0.4258	0.0955	14.6881	2.9596
87	öl -bit	die -PSTPT	V	15	0.0007	90.0	8	0.3575	0.1150	15.5571	5.5624
88	kös -an	migrate -PF.CVB	V	15	0.0007	90.0	8	0.3168	0.0694	16.4947	3.6024
89	sarsıarda	morning	N	15	0.0007	90.0	8	0.5439	0.0889	16.9330	3.4417
90	kel -ar	come -PRSPT	V	15	0.0007	90.0	8	0.3822	0.1152	14.0899	3.8220
91	χa:l -an	remain -PF.CVB	V	15	0.0007	90.0	7	0.3740	0.0928	17.0553	4.5547
92	taŋas	clothes	N	15	0.0007	90.0	6	0.4096	0.1256	13.0009	2.9164
93	saχa -lar	Sakha -PL	N	15	0.0007	90.0	5	0.4496	0.1031	16.2431	3.2836
94	taγıls -a	go.up -IPF.CVB	V	14	0.0007	99.0	8	0.3683	0.0541	13.9128	2.5540
95	çjıj -(i)nan	authenticity -INST	N	14	0.0007	99.0	8	0.4554	0.1247	16.3427	3.9929
96	çjon -(n)i	people -ACC	N	14	0.0007	99.0	8	0.3169	0.0561	12.9929	2.2982
97	oγo -(n)i	child -ACC	N	14	0.0007	99.0	8	0.3351	0.0823	15.7859	3.8524
98	olor -bit	sit -PSTPT	V	14	0.0007	99.0	7	0.5791	0.1538	12.8458	3.1594
99	il -an	take -PF.CVB	V	14	0.0007	99.0	7	0.3044	0.0887	14.2871	4.4774
100	sirıt -bit -(i)m	go -PSTPT -POSS.1SG	V	14	0.0007	99.0	7	0.6551	0.1443	15.9750	3.5596

Table 11: The 100 most frequent word types in Texistepec

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	ø- du'k	3:B- llegar	V	120	0.0039	1.0	5	0.2147	0.0714	20.7680	7.0129
2	n- sun	1/3- querer	V	98	0.0031	2.0	5	0.2422	0.1057	19.5290	8.3149
3	y- bêñ	3:A- venir	V	87	0.0028	3.0	4	0.2103	0.0799	16.5425	6.5541
4	ø- dāk	3:B- ir	V	85	0.0027	4.0	5	0.1840	0.0738	18.7053	6.7355
5	pääñ	hombre	N	76	0.0024	5.0	5	0.2682	0.0965	17.0621	6.6694
6	y- dām	3:A- decir	V	75	0.0024	6.0	6	0.1714	0.0627	25.8248	7.4629
7	jikante	gigante	N	73	0.0023	7.0	2	0.5197	0.1221	14.2363	3.4754
8	rey	rey	N	72	0.0023	8.0	2	0.2885	0.0878	11.4177	3.8686
9	ø- dāk -am	3:B- ir -ya	V	61	0.0020	9.0	5	0.2924	0.0774	18.3609	5.1351
10	jaa	día	N	54	0.0017	10.0	6	0.2036	0.0877	17.7177	7.8281
11	ny- wat	2/3- hacer	V	49	0.0016	11.0	4	0.2203	0.0613	24.6835	7.6414
12	yoomä'	mujer	N	46	0.0015	12.0	6	0.4001	0.1014	15.9502	4.0789
13	y- wat	3/3- hacer	V	45	0.0014	13.0	5	0.2379	0.0859	18.9042	6.4619
14	y- sun	3/3- querer	V	43	0.0014	14.5	5	0.2740	0.1056	20.2200	5.8636
15	yoos	trabajo	N	43	0.0014	14.5	4	0.3155	0.0779	13.5285	3.7641
16	ø- dāk -yaj	3:B- ir -3:PL	V	42	0.0013	16.0	5	0.3234	0.0925	20.0914	5.7467
17	'eeche	nada	N	41	0.0013	17.0	5	0.3026	0.0897	18.0819	6.2519
18	ny- sun	2/3- querer	V	40	0.0013	18.0	5	0.2597	0.0641	24.5715	6.3884
19	soldau	soldado	N	39	0.0013	19.0	2	0.4624	0.1248	14.3258	5.4370
20	däks -ä'	irse -IMP	V	34	0.0011	20.5	5	0.3045	0.0750	20.9685	5.5561
21	n- jaay - tääw	1:A- macho - hermano	N	34	0.0011	20.5	4	0.3950	0.1204	22.2989	7.2133
22	kn- dām -a'	1/2- decir -APL	V	33	0.0011	23.0	6	0.3465	0.0897	18.4653	4.7801
23	n- baan	1:A- hijo	N	33	0.0011	23.0	5	0.3508	0.1090	12.6016	4.3051
24	däk	ir	V	33	0.0011	23.0	3	0.1625	0.0532	20.6619	7.3221
25	n- wat	1/3- hacer	V	32	0.0010	26.0	5	0.2182	0.0772	21.3026	9.5530
26	k- dāk -p	1:B- ir -FUT	V	32	0.0010	26.0	4	0.2956	0.0713	17.9936	4.9041
27	jente	gente	N	32	0.0010	26.0	4	0.4319	0.0854	12.3060	4.2282
28	y- dāk	3:A- ir	V	31	0.0010	28.0	4	0.2066	0.0778	22.4394	9.1369
29	n- be'tz	1/3- buscar	V	29	0.0009	29.0	4	0.2884	0.0884	18.7284	5.0097
30	y- dām -a'	3/3- decir -APL	V	28	0.0009	31.0	5	0.3156	0.0972	21.0798	7.6441
31	y- tāk -ä	3:A- casa -LOC	N	28	0.0009	31.0	5	0.3298	0.1076	16.6541	5.0780
32	dä'	agua	N	28	0.0009	31.0	3	0.2298	0.0794	14.3880	4.4314
33	n- wat -p	1/3- hacer -FUT	V	27	0.0009	35.5	5	0.2443	0.0871	22.6619	6.8256
34	tej	vamos	V	27	0.0009	35.5	5	0.2241	0.0878	15.5399	6.2304
35	ø- 'o'tz -de'	3:B- sentar -EST	V	27	0.0009	35.5	5	0.4020	0.1006	18.5419	4.8269
36	ø- wêch -e'	3:B- caminar -DEP	V	27	0.0009	35.5	4	0.4274	0.1065	17.5390	4.9981
37	tumeen	dinero	N	27	0.0009	35.5	3	0.4113	0.1035	15.5280	4.1911
38	teniente	teniente	N	27	0.0009	35.5	1	0.5600	0.1203	14.9422	3.2608
39	y- yoomä' -baa	3:A- mujer -DIM	N	26	0.0008	39.5	4	0.4541	0.0897	18.3425	3.9814
40	n- dāk	1:A- ir	V	26	0.0008	39.5	3	0.2188	0.0407	14.1500	2.5273
41	ø- du'k -yaj	3:B- llegar -3:PL	V	25	0.0008	41.5	5	0.3185	0.0953	24.2371	8.5743
42	y- yaka'	3/3- matar	V	25	0.0008	41.5	4	0.3616	0.1343	21.8350	7.5141
43	y- 'esh	3/3- ver	V	24	0.0008	43.5	5	0.1861	0.1010	20.9842	10.6627

Table 11: The 100 most frequent word types in Texistepec (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
44	ø- mēñ	3:B- venir	V	24	0.0008	43.5	4	0.2510	0.0877	13.4142	4.9504
45	ky- dāk -p	2:B- ir -FUT	V	23	0.0007	46.0	5	0.3083	0.1283	22.4980	8.1293
46	ø- dāk -e'	3:B- ir -DEP	V	23	0.0007	46.0	4	0.3303	0.1022	19.8409	5.9191
47	suutu'	muchacho	N	23	0.0007	46.0	4	0.3572	0.0830	17.6125	3.8610
48	k- seet -p	1:B- volver -FUT	V	21	0.0007	48.5	2	0.4452	0.0824	13.9578	2.7976
49	wē'k -p	comer -FUT	V	21	0.0007	48.5	1	0.2462	0.0351	20.7401	3.2789
50	n- 'ēsh	1/3- saber	V	20	0.0006	52.0	5	0.1892	0.0899	30.8092	11.2039
51	ø- tzak -ä'	3:B- dejar -IMP	V	20	0.0006	52.0	5	0.3870	0.1167	19.5653	5.4426
52	y- duuñe'	3:A- mujer	N	20	0.0006	52.0	4	0.4235	0.0975	19.8391	4.5470
53	ø- täkeñ	3:B- entrar	V	20	0.0006	52.0	4	0.3180	0.1024	17.4915	6.1018
54	n- täk	1:A- casa	N	20	0.0006	52.0	3	0.2687	0.0834	16.4453	5.7392
55	ø- put	3:B- salir	V	18	0.0006	57.5	5	0.2414	0.0614	13.2242	3.4618
56	y- 'boom	3:A- papá	N	18	0.0006	57.5	4	0.3456	0.0947	15.7281	5.1372
57	ny- wat -p	2/3- hacer -FUT	V	18	0.0006	57.5	3	0.2581	0.0895	25.3202	6.5096
58	ny- 'ēsh	2/3- ver	V	18	0.0006	57.5	3	0.1804	0.0688	31.9847	12.6018
59	das - yuku	pueblo - en	N	18	0.0006	57.5	3	0.4704	0.1395	16.0991	4.7832
60	ky- ka'	2:B- morir	V	18	0.0006	57.5	2	0.2506	0.0648	21.6380	7.2031
61	yoomä' - suutu'	mujer - joven	N	17	0.0005	61.5	4	0.5796	0.1858	16.6612	4.0134
62	pooy	mes	N	17	0.0005	61.5	4	0.3801	0.1427	11.8378	4.0179
63	tyempu	tiempo	N	16	0.0005	66.5	5	0.4740	0.1027	13.1094	2.2798
64	ø- dāk -yaj -am	3:B- ir -3:PL -ya	V	16	0.0005	66.5	5	0.4399	0.1169	19.5454	5.7003
65	n- 'ēsh -p	1/3- saber -FUT	V	16	0.0005	66.5	5	0.2070	0.0478	30.4070	6.7591
66	mēñ -ä'	venir -IMP	V	16	0.0005	66.5	4	0.3646	0.0634	16.9395	3.0072
67	gaayu	gallo	N	16	0.0005	66.5	4	0.4006	0.1456	14.0131	5.2670
68	ø- jak	3:B- pasar	V	16	0.0005	66.5	4	0.2277	0.0672	13.9568	3.0911
69	y- dāks -da' -yaj	3/3- irse -CAUS -3:PL	V	16	0.0005	66.5	3	0.4599	0.1314	23.3066	6.1180
70	booya'	flor	N	16	0.0005	66.5	2	0.3600	0.0864	17.7542	4.9739
71	y- tzak	3/3- dejar	V	15	0.0005	73.0	4	0.2661	0.0457	19.3368	3.4550
72	ø- yaj	3:B- acabar	V	15	0.0005	73.0	4	0.2296	0.0597	14.4787	6.1921
73	ø- 'a'm -ä'	3:B- ver -IMP	V	15	0.0005	73.0	4	0.3401	0.0666	18.2513	3.4127
74	ø- seet	3:B- regresar	V	15	0.0005	73.0	3	0.2788	0.0799	15.3013	3.7733
75	dios	Dios	N	15	0.0005	73.0	3	0.3693	0.1213	12.2650	5.3516
76	y- batäj	3/3- escuchar	V	14	0.0004	81.5	5	0.4376	0.1213	14.9120	4.8386
77	y- dāks -da'	3/3- irse -CAUS	V	14	0.0004	81.5	5	0.3844	0.0777	21.7367	5.0695
78	n- yaka' -p	1/3- matar -FUT	V	14	0.0004	81.5	5	0.4024	0.0982	21.2341	6.2523
79	wē'k -ä'	comer -IMP	V	14	0.0004	81.5	4	0.4824	0.1240	15.4168	3.9471
80	ny- yaka' -p	2/3- matar -FUT	V	14	0.0004	81.5	4	0.3771	0.0947	22.3578	5.0498
81	ny- yoomä' -baa	2:A- mujer -DIM	N	14	0.0004	81.5	4	0.4287	0.0871	16.9816	3.5168
82	n- bēñ	1:A- venir	V	14	0.0004	81.5	4	0.2789	0.0653	11.4546	3.3210
83	y- bēñ -yaj	3:A- venir -3:PL	V	14	0.0004	81.5	3	0.3466	0.0920	15.5557	4.9116
84	k- bēñ	1:B- venir	V	14	0.0004	81.5	3	0.2568	0.0954	17.7051	6.7036
85	ø- ka'	3:B- morir	V	14	0.0004	81.5	3	0.2039	0.0456	15.5322	4.0274

Table 11: The 100 most frequent word types in Texistepec (*continued*)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	rank	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
86	n- 'oom	1:A- papá	N	14	0.0004	81.5	2	0.3949	0.1520	14.0710	4.1902
87	y- tuj -ku'	3:A- tirar -INSTR	V	14	0.0004	81.5	2	0.3888	0.0675	21.2091	3.9656
88	ny- jaam	2/3- saber	V	13	0.0004	89.5	3	0.3353	0.0845	19.3647	6.8976
89	y- 'otāŋ	3:A- hablar	V	13	0.0004	89.5	2	0.3375	0.0821	18.7097	4.3025
90	du'up	zopilote	N	13	0.0004	89.5	1	0.3583	0.0926	14.8272	3.7506
91	mandar	mandar	V	13	0.0004	89.5	1	0.4643	0.0837	13.3155	2.3840
92	ø- du'k -am	3:B- llegar -ya	V	12	0.0004	94.0	4	0.3466	0.0636	18.0280	4.3846
93	y- jääk - put	3/3- jalar - salir	V	12	0.0004	94.0	4	0.5079	0.0890	14.3161	3.4335
94	n- wat -a' -p	1/3- hacer -APL -FUT	V	12	0.0004	94.0	4	0.4157	0.1213	20.5693	6.0154
95	ø- boŋ -e'	3:B- dormir -DEP	V	12	0.0004	94.0	3	0.3174	0.0604	19.5983	4.0593
96	n- yoomäi' -baa	1:A- mujer -DIM	N	12	0.0004	94.0	3	0.4483	0.1272	16.5968	3.8310
97	y- put -da'	3/3- salir -CAUS	V	11	0.0004	105.0	5	0.3929	0.0617	18.1808	2.5757
98	y- du'k	3:A- llegar	V	11	0.0004	105.0	4	0.3238	0.0768	19.3106	3.7638
99	ø- tzä'y	3:B- quedar	V	11	0.0004	105.0	4	0.2452	0.0474	21.1701	4.5348
100	y- 'oota'	3/3- hablar	V	11	0.0004	105.0	4	0.4095	0.1213	18.7072	6.1845

B. Lists of excluded word types in the ten languages

Table 12: Excluded word types in Baure

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	kwe'	exist	V	80	0.0046	18	0.2951	0.1339	15.1122	5.4347
2	ro = ke -wo =ji	3SGm = EV -COP = QUOT	V	79	0.0045	10	0.4921	0.1176	15.0370	3.1138
3	ro = ke -wo	3SGm = EV -COP	V	29	0.0017	16	0.4190	0.1258	12.8172	3.2350
4	ri = ke -wo =ji	3SGf = EV -COP = QUOT	V	22	0.0013	10	0.4907	0.1104	15.7156	2.9946
5	wo -no -wo	be -NMLZ -COP	V	15	0.0009	9	0.3588	0.0524	14.4426	2.4914
6	no = ke -wo =ji	3PL = EV -COP = QUOT	V	15	0.0009	4	0.5787	0.1226	13.0872	2.8591
7	kwore'	he.is	V	14	0.0008	7	0.5936	0.3615	12.6196	4.8842
8	ro = wo -wo	3SGm = be -COP	V	12	0.0007	5	0.3359	0.0815	16.1362	5.9898
9	kwe' =ji	exist = QUOT	V	10	0.0006	6	0.3724	0.1545	16.9435	6.2817
10	wo -no	be -NMLZ	V	10	0.0006	5	0.2230	0.0668	16.6647	7.3981
11	pi = ke	2SG = EV	V	9	0.0005	4	0.4737	0.1690	10.1966	2.6653
12	ri = wo -wo	3SGf = be -COP	V	9	0.0005	3	0.4111	0.0827	13.1412	2.6073

Table 13: Excluded word types in Bora

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	ijcya -ne	be -INAN	V	91	0.0032	27	0.4309	0.1261	17.9099	5.9310
2	lljchuífhyo	Pucunero	N	74	0.0026	3	0.6001	0.1593	16.6757	3.8401
3	ijcya -vbe	be -M.SG	V	58	0.0020	17	0.5001	0.1482	20.6192	23.8943
4	nee -ne	be -INAN	V	35	0.0012	18	0.3346	0.1122	18.0869	10.6250
5	ijcya -hi	be -PRED	V	28	0.0010	12	0.4731	0.1511	16.4411	5.8139
6	ijcya -náa	be -SIM	V	27	0.0009	7	0.4736	0.1388	18.6571	6.7305
7	ijcya	be	V	20	0.0007	9	0.2674	0.1276	25.9737	20.9130
8	nee -vbe	be -M.SG	V	17	0.0006	7	0.4156	0.1090	13.3574	3.9629
9	ijcya -tu	be -NEG	V	16	0.0006	10	0.4111	0.1623	23.5052	19.1856
10	ijcya -me	be -PL	V	14	0.0005	10	0.3983	0.1590	22.9613	17.5251
11	ijcya -híjcyá	be -REP	V	13	0.0005	6	0.5018	0.1768	24.8524	18.4380
12	ijcya -nejcu	be -CLF.side	V	12	0.0004	7	0.6544	0.1462	14.5474	4.0441

Table 14: Excluded word types in Chintang

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	yuj -no	be.there -IND.NPST	V	40	0.0011	16	0.2747	0.1291	21.2153	6.6572
2	lis -no	be -IND.NPST	V	38	0.0010	16	0.3141	0.1251	16.6386	6.7420
3	lis -e	be -IND.PST	V	36	0.0010	14	0.3132	0.1296	15.0001	4.9626
4	chintaŋ	a.place	N	35	0.0009	9	0.4364	0.1928	18.5441	6.1111
5	yuj -a -yakt -e	be -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	26	0.0007	6	0.3939	0.1277	19.3120	5.2263
6	par -ne	should -NPST.PTCP	V	24	0.0006	12	0.3608	0.1238	15.3706	5.0551
7	yuj -a -yakt -e	be.there -PST -IPFV -IND.PST	V	23	0.0006	7	0.4828	0.2504	17.4980	6.8444
8	kond -no	should -IND.NPST	V	23	0.0006	5	0.3156	0.1325	19.3613	5.6841
9	yuj -no	be -IND.NPST	V	19	0.0005	9	0.2940	0.0954	19.0868	5.5560
10	yuj -a -yakt -e	be -PST -IPFV -PST	V	19	0.0005	7	0.4328	0.1175	17.4707	5.4329
11	lis -i	be -1/2pS/P	V	16	0.0004	3	0.2606	0.0786	16.6031	4.5520
12	yuj -no	be -NPST	V	15	0.0004	7	0.4362	0.1498	13.2550	5.9594
13	lis -e	be -PST	V	14	0.0004	6	0.3436	0.1157	13.0026	4.8849

Table 15: Excluded word types in Chintang (no pear stories)

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	chintaŋ	a.place	N	35	0.0009	9	0.4364	0.1928	18.5441	6.1111
2	lis -no	be -IND.NPST	V	20	0.0005	7	0.3367	0.1205	15.0240	6.1163
3	kond -no	should -IND.NPST	V	20	0.0005	4	0.3290	0.1367	18.8806	5.8297
4	yuj -a -yakt -e	be -PST -IPFV -PST	V	19	0.0005	7	0.4328	0.1175	17.4707	5.4329
5	par -ne	should -NPST.PTCP	V	18	0.0005	8	0.3433	0.0913	15.6843	4.7578
6	lis -i	be -1/2pS/P	V	16	0.0004	3	0.2606	0.0786	16.6031	4.5520
7	yuj -no	be -NPST	V	15	0.0004	7	0.4362	0.1498	13.2550	5.9594
8	lis -e	be -PST	V	14	0.0004	6	0.3436	0.1157	13.0026	4.8849
9	lis -e	be -IND.PST	V	14	0.0004	4	0.3021	0.0878	15.0533	4.5464
10	yuj -no	be -IND.NPST	V	10	0.0003	3	0.2566	0.0563	21.5896	5.0262
11	yuj -no	be.there -IND.NPST	V	10	0.0003	3	0.2670	0.1177	21.1941	5.5923

Table 16: Excluded word types in Dutch

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	is	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	641	0.0162	17	0.1426	0.0682	17.6453	10.0985
2	heb	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	264	0.0067	17	0.1436	0.0460	23.4406	9.9210
3	was	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	194	0.0049	17	0.1775	0.0573	18.5940	6.0182
4	moet	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	183	0.0046	17	0.1609	0.0545	27.7604	9.4714
5	zijn	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	153	0.0039	17	0.2085	0.0671	21.0536	6.4172
6	had	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	135	0.0034	16	0.1550	0.0629	21.9302	7.5194
7	kan	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	123	0.0031	17	0.1676	0.0489	19.5087	6.3030
8	's	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	117	0.0030	17	0.0900	0.0483	14.0761	7.8951
9	ben	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	106	0.0027	17	0.1655	0.0621	20.4236	6.8900
10	doen	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	101	0.0026	17	0.2019	0.0761	23.2154	11.4999
11	hebben	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	96	0.0024	17	0.1832	0.0702	37.5695	14.3306
12	heeft	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	91	0.0023	17	0.1996	0.0736	28.3538	10.4522
13	zou	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	69	0.0017	15	0.1542	0.0550	22.4177	9.9823
14	hebt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	57	0.0014	14	0.1737	0.0795	28.0883	13.7310
15	wil	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	57	0.0014	14	0.1577	0.0474	20.9955	7.9007
16	hadden	WW(pv,verl,mv)	V	46	0.0012	14	0.2017	0.0718	33.0027	10.6451
17	zijn	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	46	0.0012	14	0.2417	0.0834	18.5396	6.8860
18	moeten	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	43	0.0011	14	0.2395	0.0855	28.3112	10.7021
19	gedaan	WW(vd,vrij,zonder)	V	43	0.0011	14	0.3614	0.0776	17.3585	3.7930
20	zal	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	42	0.0011	15	0.1764	0.0485	18.1957	4.6161
21	wordt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	42	0.0011	13	0.1954	0.0748	28.7266	9.3415
22	kun	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	38	0.0010	15	0.1356	0.0323	23.6099	6.8701
23	doe	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	35	0.0009	12	0.1170	0.0508	30.4911	13.5389
24	waren	WW(pv,verl,mv)	V	33	0.0008	14	0.2358	0.0889	23.5004	7.1470
25	gehad	WW(vd,vrij,zonder)	V	31	0.0008	12	0.2925	0.0677	18.1480	4.9264
26	bent	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	29	0.0007	15	0.2206	0.0919	21.4477	9.8398
27	kunnen	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	29	0.0007	11	0.2239	0.0547	28.3150	6.7818
28	hebben	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	29	0.0007	11	0.2533	0.0659	25.5433	8.0974
29	geweest	WW(vd,vrij,zonder)	V	26	0.0007	11	0.4302	0.1123	17.2318	3.9252
30	kunnen	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	25	0.0006	12	0.2568	0.0720	24.8995	5.9166
31	kunt	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	23	0.0006	12	0.2219	0.0571	19.2583	5.2700
32	mag	WW(pv,tgw,ev)	V	20	0.0005	8	0.1714	0.0288	18.2232	4.8196
33	worden	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	18	0.0005	10	0.2931	0.0667	21.3623	4.2520
34	doet	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	17	0.0004	8	0.2117	0.0557	20.4585	6.7205
35	kon	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	16	0.0004	9	0.1591	0.0347	19.9022	5.2599
36	doen	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	16	0.0004	5	0.1870	0.0788	24.4419	8.4394
37	moest	WW(pv,verl,ev)	V	15	0.0004	8	0.2168	0.0664	25.9721	10.7767
38	moeten	WW(Inf,vrij,zonder)	V	13	0.0003	10	0.2390	0.0498	26.2041	5.9916
39	worden	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	13	0.0003	6	0.2562	0.0861	25.7317	7.9463
40	zullen	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	12	0.0003	10	0.1864	0.0412	33.8906	8.5211
41	willen	WW(pv,tgw,mv)	V	12	0.0003	7	0.2447	0.0733	26.6261	8.1942
42	hoeft	WW(pv,tgw,met-t)	V	12	0.0003	6	0.1484	0.0537	41.1527	22.9768
43	moesten	WW(pv,verl,mv)	V	12	0.0003	5	0.2988	0.0574	24.3496	5.2791

Table 17: Excluded word types in English

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	do	do.INF	V	743	0.0132	47	0.1683	0.0928	15.4019	7.8239
2	have	have.INF	V	577	0.0103	47	0.2111	0.1030	22.5251	9.0588
3	is	be.3sg.PRES	V	449	0.0080	47	0.1958	0.1179	13.7044	8.0530
4	was	be.PAST	V	412	0.0073	44	0.1922	0.0840	17.9804	6.3078
5	be	be.INF	V	299	0.0053	46	0.1626	0.0844	14.9145	5.9459
6	're	be.PRES	V	298	0.0053	44	0.0613	0.0521	47.4278	21.7422
7	are	be.PRES	V	262	0.0047	45	0.1622	0.1031	26.6932	16.8941
8	'm	be.PRES	V	256	0.0046	43	0.0772	0.0519	17.5366	8.9897
9	get	get.INF	V	243	0.0043	46	0.1827	0.0718	18.1387	5.3235
10	had	have.PAST	V	175	0.0031	34	0.2211	0.0958	15.6964	5.7202
11	've	have.INF	V	157	0.0028	43	0.0508	0.0305	49.0407	19.1753
12	did	do.PAST	V	153	0.0027	35	0.2059	0.0871	16.9512	6.2874
13	it	it	N	116	0.0021	42	0.1508	0.0623	15.4410	6.1589
14	were	be.PAST	V	114	0.0020	30	0.1534	0.0657	30.7623	12.4858
15	been	be.PPART	V	100	0.0018	32	0.1959	0.0715	22.8920	7.6845
16	has	have.3sg.PRES	V	93	0.0017	31	0.2330	0.0957	15.4572	7.8547
17	got	get.PAST	V	69	0.0012	33	0.2072	0.0631	15.6827	4.4058
18	does	do.3sg.PRES	V	54	0.0010	27	0.2429	0.0789	18.1457	5.6779
19	be -ing	be -PROG	V	53	0.0009	22	0.2768	0.1073	19.9503	5.4814
20	get -ing	get -PROG	V	50	0.0009	25	0.3055	0.1027	25.1138	7.2029
21	t	t	N	37	0.0007	17	0.2529	0.1000	4.4465	1.5597
22	am	be.PRES	V	36	0.0006	16	0.1861	0.1081	14.6523	8.0973
23	texas	texas	N	27	0.0005	15	0.5189	0.1252	10.1589	2.3188
24	i	i	N	23	0.0004	9	0.2214	0.0903	5.1225	1.7752
25	dallas	dallas	N	20	0.0004	12	0.4930	0.1307	13.0125	3.4244

Table 18: Excluded word types in Even

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	bi -ri -n(i)	be -pst -poss.3sg	V	230	0.0062	40	0.3540	0.1362	15.7079	4.8227
2	bi -če	be -pf.ptc	V	168	0.0045	32	0.3228	0.0764	13.0283	2.7895
3	bi -r(e) -n(i)	be -nonfut -3sg	V	132	0.0035	40	0.3859	0.1069	13.9947	3.8747
4	bi -gr(e) -n(i)	be -hab -3sg	V	60	0.0016	25	0.4423	0.1171	14.4878	3.7013
5	bi -r(e) -m	be -nonfut -1sg	V	57	0.0015	27	0.3326	0.1065	16.6485	5.9871
6	bi -de -n(i)	be -purp.cvb -poss.3sg	V	42	0.0011	16	0.4006	0.0944	13.1919	3.1929
7	bi -ri -ten	be -pst -poss.3pl	V	42	0.0011	14	0.4790	0.0854	16.9249	2.8546
8	bi -če -l	be -pf.ptc -pl	V	41	0.0011	12	0.3777	0.0895	13.9614	3.1830
9	bi -rek -e -n(i)	be -cond.cvb -ep -poss.3sg	V	38	0.0010	15	0.4627	0.1150	16.0227	4.2563
10	o: -n(i)	become -3sg	V	37	0.0010	22	0.3527	0.1094	15.1742	5.0000
11	bi -r(e) -p	be -nonfut -1pl.in	V	30	0.0008	16	0.3295	0.0794	16.0301	3.7557
12	o: -če	become -pf.ptc	V	30	0.0008	16	0.3379	0.0710	12.3336	2.5404
13	bi -ri -w	be -pst -poss.1sg	V	26	0.0007	13	0.3929	0.1309	13.7300	3.5362
14	o: -niken	become -sim.cvb	V	26	0.0007	13	0.4550	0.1136	16.4739	4.7862
15	bi -r(e)	be -nonfut	V	23	0.0006	17	0.3522	0.0821	12.0703	2.7241
16	bi -ri -t(i)	be -pst -poss.1pl.in	V	23	0.0006	15	0.3886	0.1107	13.9537	4.1770
17	omčeni	Emčeni	N	22	0.0006	1	0.5259	0.1274	12.0067	2.6492
18	bi -gr(e) -če	be -hab -pf.ptc	V	21	0.0006	7	0.5012	0.0563	14.1433	1.6710
19	bi -r	be -neg.cvb	V	20	0.0005	15	0.2689	0.0820	16.1173	4.5343
20	bi -r(e) -nri	be -nonfut -2sg	V	19	0.0005	11	0.4913	0.1800	15.9432	5.1261
21	bi -we:č -ri -w	be -gnr -pst -poss.1sg	V	18	0.0005	8	0.5759	0.0799	13.3172	2.0285
22	bi -ŋsi -j	be -impf.cvb -prfl.sg	V	17	0.0005	12	0.5004	0.1477	14.4373	4.4946
23	o: -dži -n(i)	become -fut -3sg	V	17	0.0005	8	0.4102	0.0685	15.0045	2.4890
24	o: -rek -e -n(i)	become -cond.cvb -ep -poss.3sg	V	16	0.0004	10	0.4654	0.1406	16.4103	5.0802
25	boč'ilikan	Bočilikan	N	16	0.0004	1	0.7102	0.0673	12.7677	1.0873
26	stepanov	Stepanov	N	15	0.0004	9	0.6677	0.1368	12.7170	2.3664
27	bi -če -dži -n(i)	be -pf.ptc -fut -3sg	V	15	0.0004	8	0.4661	0.0866	19.9611	4.9173
28	o: -če -l	become -pf.ptc -pl	V	15	0.0004	8	0.3728	0.0802	13.9033	2.4904

Table 19: Excluded word types in Hoocak

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	haa = ra	have.kin(OBJ.3SG)\1E.A = NMLZ	V	74	0.0032	20	0.3549	0.1282	16.0144	5.8735
2	wa-hii	OBJ.3PL-make/CAUS(SBJ.3SG)	V	26	0.0011	8	0.5058	0.1721	9.1773	3.2722
3	wa-haa = ra	OBJ.3PL-have.kin\1E.A = NMLZ	V	23	0.0010	11	0.4848	0.1530	15.3852	4.0676
4	haa = ra	have.kin\1E.A = NMLZ	V	19	0.0008	8	0.4267	0.1241	12.4354	2.8073
5	hii	make/CAUS(SBJ.3SG&OBJ.3SG)	V	14	0.0006	8	0.2971	0.1261	11.9706	5.4858
6	wa-hanĭ-wi = ra	OBJ.3PL-have.NTL\1E.A-PL = NMLZ	V	13	0.0006	2	0.6278	0.1846	15.4090	4.1363
7	hanĭ	have.NTL(SBJ.3SG&OBJ.3SG)	V	12	0.0005	9	0.2963	0.0914	14.8585	5.0803
8	hii-ire	make/CAUS(OBJ.3SG)-SBJ.3PL	V	12	0.0005	7	0.3881	0.1409	14.5481	5.2395
9	ha-nĭhe	1E.A-be/PROG	V	12	0.0005	6	0.6509	0.1066	9.4443	1.5215
10	haa	make/CAUS(OBJ.3SG)\1E.A	V	11	0.0005	10	0.3872	0.1137	8.2910	2.4339

There were no excluded auxiliaries or other, specifically excluded words in N||ng.

Table 20: Excluded word types in Sakha

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	e -ta	be -PST.3SG	V	233	0.0109	16	0.2744	0.0855	12.1421	4.3970
2	suoχ	non-existence	V	212	0.0099	16	0.3194	0.1175	14.9124	13.6576
3	barr	existence	V	145	0.0068	16	0.2694	0.0672	15.7305	3.8340
4	buol -an	AUX -PF.CVB	V	129	0.0061	15	0.3654	0.0932	17.4738	4.5437
5	e -bit	be -PSTPT	V	113	0.0053	15	0.3201	0.1057	14.0043	5.0772
6	buol -taχ -(t)a	AUX -MDL -POSS.3SG	V	100	0.0047	13	0.2885	0.1594	22.0544	11.8174
7	buol -ia	AUX -FUT.3SG	V	52	0.0024	13	0.3604	0.1004	18.8147	11.0372
8	e -ti -(i)m	be -PST -POSS.1SG	V	50	0.0023	9	0.3203	0.0784	13.4614	4.6224
9	buol -ta	AUX -PST.3SG	V	48	0.0023	12	0.3867	0.0921	16.4439	4.1282
10	buol -ar	AUX -PRSPT	V	46	0.0022	11	0.3717	0.0779	16.9337	4.0278
11	kiāj -an	be.able -PF.CVB	V	40	0.0019	12	0.3415	0.0759	18.3353	3.6954
12	buol -tar	AUX -COND	V	33	0.0015	11	0.3606	0.0853	20.5151	5.0381
13	barr -lar	existence -PL	V	30	0.0014	13	0.4479	0.0953	16.3317	3.5047
14	e -ti -bit	be -PST -1PL	V	23	0.0011	10	0.4478	0.1449	14.9381	5.3514
15	ǰokuskaj -ga	Y. -DAT	N	23	0.0011	6	0.7141	0.1483	15.9298	2.7466
16	e -bit -(t)a	be -PSTPT -POSS.3SG	V	20	0.0009	7	0.3115	0.0652	16.7758	3.7994
17	buol -a	AUX -IPF.CVB	V	19	0.0009	10	0.2912	0.0438	17.5711	2.8266
18	na:da	have.to.R	V	19	0.0009	6	0.3876	0.0819	13.4550	2.8725
19	buol -taχ -ina	AUX -MDL -COND.3SG	V	15	0.0007	7	0.5033	0.1535	21.7583	6.8855
20	kebis -ar -lar	PFV -PRSPT -PL	V	15	0.0007	5	0.4936	0.1500	22.1768	8.7461
21	er -taχ -pina	be -MDL -COND.1SG	V	14	0.0007	8	0.5721	0.1481	16.7265	4.9884
22	suoχ -(t)a	non-existence -POSS.3SG	V	14	0.0007	8	0.3314	0.0955	18.7040	15.3915

Table 21: Excluded word types in Textistepec

	word type	gloss	word class	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	doc. freq.	mean duration	std. dev.	mean art. rate	std. dev.
1	∅- 'êch	3:B- estar	V	180	0.0058	5	0.1965	0.0688	17.3763	6.5431
2	y- 'êch	3:A- estar	V	94	0.0030	6	0.1680	0.0721	19.9794	7.1986
3	jwaŋ	Juan	N	60	0.0019	3	0.3426	0.0971	12.6330	3.6656
4	y- 'êch -da'	3/3- estar -CAUS	V	31	0.0010	5	0.3333	0.0815	18.9840	4.2904
5	'êch -e'	estar -DEP	V	31	0.0010	4	0.4077	0.1334	16.3919	5.5355
6	y- wêñ	3:A- REFL	N	25	0.0008	5	0.1886	0.0860	18.8215	7.3612
7	n- 'êch -da'	1/3- estar -CAUS	V	23	0.0007	3	0.3421	0.1017	25.2609	7.0694
8	k- 'êch	1:B- estar	V	18	0.0006	4	0.2286	0.0366	22.4125	3.6766
9	ny- 'êch -da'	2/3- estar -CAUS	V	14	0.0004	5	0.3132	0.0871	27.1348	6.2874
10	y- 'êch -da' -pä'	3/3- estar -CAUS -REL	V	13	0.0004	2	0.4098	0.0789	22.5666	3.4830
11	∅- 'êch -yaj -e'	3:B- estar -3:PL -DEP	V	12	0.0004	2	0.4353	0.1156	17.1034	4.3019
12	flojo	Flojo	N	12	0.0004	1	0.3793	0.1015	14.0883	3.8138

C. Distribution of word frequencies (Zipf plots)

Figure 1: Rank vs. frequency for content words in the ten languages

D. Details on the individual mixed-effects models for the ten languages

Baure

Table 22: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Baure

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	df	p
(Intercept)	-1.4322	0.0949	-15.0962							
log word frequency	-0.0681	0.0099	-6.8859	-0.1597	5.8441	1.3303	0.0244	46.9589	1	0.0000 ***
word length	0.0819	0.0051	16.1734	0.6737	34.4366	5.8838	0.1235	243.9230	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.0060	0.0123	0.4881	0.0250	-0.1241	-0.0549	0.0001	0.2094	1	0.6472 n.s.
position	0.0889	0.0195	4.5663	0.0893	1.8783	1.7010	0.0104	20.7434	1	0.0000 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.1549	0.0202	-7.6663	-0.2136	5.9740	4.6951	0.0293	58.0437	1	0.0000 ***
log speech rate	-0.1053	0.0225	-4.6821	-0.0898	1.8094	0.6231	0.0115	21.1237	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 1\,924$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.3239$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.3552$

Table 23: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Baure

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	df	p
speaker	11	0.0496	-1.2626	0.4231	0.5671	1	0.4514 n.s.
text	37	0.0416	1.5021	1.4383	6.6998	1	0.0096 **
Residual		0.2941					

Bora

Table 24: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Bora

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-1.0499	0.0803	-13.0697							
log word frequency	0.0020	0.0090	0.2183	0.0038	-0.0213	-0.0273	0.0000	0.0484	1	0.8259 n.s.
word length	0.1408	0.0056	25.3444	0.5923	38.0563	32.1583	0.1739	580.5155	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	-0.0419	0.0130	-3.2312	-0.0801	0.4307	0.5596	0.0035	10.4310	1	0.0012 **
position	-0.0259	0.0196	-1.3248	-0.0190	0.0519	0.0706	0.0006	1.7560	1	0.1851 n.s.
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.0024	0.0163	-0.1466	-0.0026	-0.0151	-0.0256	0.0000	0.0220	1	0.8820 n.s.
log speech rate	-0.2535	0.0200	-12.6500	-0.2021	12.3645	7.0005	0.0601	155.9144	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 2\ 863$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.3556$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.4108$

Table 25: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Bora

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
speaker	31	0.0679	0.1077	-0.1721	4.7794	1	0.0288 *
text	37	0.0781	-0.3221	1.5743	41.5189	1	0.0000 ***
Residual		0.3379					

Chintang

Table 26: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Chintang

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-1.0094	0.0903	-11.1835							
log word frequency	0.0390	0.0105	3.7239	0.0660	2.0194	1.1119	0.0049	13.8766	1	0.0002 ***
word length	0.1122	0.0051	22.0520	0.4399	56.2432	43.7402	0.1467	442.4994	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.0628	0.0146	4.3079	0.1140	2.7733	0.7824	0.0065	18.4329	1	0.0000 ***
position	0.1365	0.0205	6.6673	0.1116	4.7834	4.6697	0.0151	44.1113	1	0.0000 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.1304	0.0206	-6.3186	-0.1475	5.1095	3.2540	0.0138	39.7466	1	0.0000 ***
log speech rate	-0.2029	0.0205	-9.9054	-0.1729	12.7666	-3.2565	0.0369	93.7366	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 2\,734$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.2328$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.2977$

Table 27: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Chintang

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
speaker	56	0.0994	-0.1608	6.5195	17.7689	1	0.0000 ***
text	40	0.0436	0.2064	-1.4633	1.4588	1	0.2271 n.s.
Residual		0.3570					

Chintang (no pear stories)

Table 28: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Chintang (no pear stories)

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-0.8951	0.1465	-6.1103							
log word frequency	0.0167	0.0161	1.0366	0.0257	0.2284	-0.0190	0.0008	1.0938	1	0.2956 n.s.
word length	0.1299	0.0084	15.4433	0.4206	43.3012	37.0427	0.1521	219.5167	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.0802	0.0202	3.9648	0.1385	2.9264	1.9397	0.0118	15.6080	1	0.0001 ***
position	-0.0648	0.0333	-1.9485	-0.0469	0.8022	0.5164	0.0028	3.7928	1	0.0515 n.s.
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.1459	0.0317	-4.6041	-0.1495	4.1954	2.1682	0.0162	21.1701	1	0.0000 ***
log speech rate	-0.3090	0.0274	-11.2703	-0.2817	26.6149	7.3070	0.0986	117.8371	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 1\,292$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.2892$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.3297$

Table 29: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Chintang (no pear stories)

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
speaker	24	0.0818	-1.8495	4.6374	15.1824	1	0.0001 ***
text	18	0.0442	0.0475	0.7941	1.0737	1	0.3001 n.s.
Residual		0.3783					

Dutch

Table 30: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Dutch

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2$ %	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2$ %	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	df	p
(Intercept)	-2.3366	0.0918	-25.4454							
log word frequency	-0.1079	0.0087	-12.4032	-0.1866	7.9001	6.6115	0.0505	149.9164	1	0 ***
word length	0.1245	0.0045	27.8392	0.4297	41.8685	34.5039	0.2165	682.0147	1	0 ***
position	0.2301	0.0198	11.6381	0.1693	7.5910	5.5764	0.0444	132.3919	1	0 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.0700	0.0136	-5.1412	-0.0775	1.9876	1.2790	0.0092	26.3902	1	0 ***
log speech rate	-0.2100	0.0236	-8.8870	-0.1342	7.6702	1.1921	0.0308	76.0387	1	0 ***

$n = 2\,694$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.41$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.465$

Table 31: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Dutch

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2$ %	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2$ %	χ^2	df	p
speaker	41	0.0929	-0.6178	3.4498	42.8783	1	0.0000 ***
text	17	0.0385	-0.0424	-0.1425	0.2352	1	0.6277 n.s.
Residual		0.3137					

English

Table 32: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in English

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	df	p
(Intercept)	-2.1138	0.0543	-38.9286							
log word frequency	-0.1197	0.0044	-26.9757	-0.2858	19.5514	16.3843	0.1045	688.2620	1	0 ***
word length	0.1174	0.0041	28.9104	0.3514	21.7815	19.9333	0.1180	783.7765	1	0 ***
number of morphemes	-0.0560	0.0136	-4.1250	-0.0481	0.4548	0.4580	0.0027	17.0002	1	0 ***
position	0.2177	0.0153	14.2590	0.1436	4.9897	4.7547	0.0308	199.9711	1	0 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.1738	0.0105	-16.5727	-0.1837	7.4276	6.0589	0.0417	268.9346	1	0 ***
log speech rate	-0.1911	0.0161	-11.8425	-0.1236	5.2302	0.9789	0.0242	134.5602	1	0 ***

$n = 6\ 136$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.3801$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.4133$

Table 33: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in English

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	df	p
speaker	80	0.0796	-0.3732	0.9072	44.3256	1	0.0000 ***
text	47	0.0304	0.1041	-0.0425	0.3093	1	0.5781 n.s.
Residual		0.3585					

Even

Table 34: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Even

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	df	p
(Intercept)	-1.4261	0.0514	-27.7408							
log word frequency	-0.0404	0.0048	-8.4555	-0.1151	3.2049	2.7168	0.0189	70.8507	1	0.0000 ***
word length	0.1197	0.0031	38.0106	0.5572	67.0652	55.6376	0.2766	1214.1003	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.0419	0.0088	4.7915	0.0786	0.8280	1.2598	0.0061	22.8423	1	0.0000 ***
position	-0.0349	0.0142	-2.4654	-0.0337	0.1680	0.3892	0.0016	6.0517	1	0.0139 *
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.0915	0.0118	-7.7668	-0.1296	2.8687	2.2874	0.0159	59.7762	1	0.0000 ***
log speech rate	-0.2063	0.0147	-14.0375	-0.1967	13.2355	4.0178	0.0582	188.6032	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 3\ 582$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.3711$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.4225$

Table 35: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Even

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	df	p
speaker	31	0.0583	-1.4253	1.641	20.3195	1	0 ***
text	67	0.0496	-1.1099	0.053	34.0922	1	0 ***
Residual		0.2567					

Hoocaq

Table 36: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Hoocaq

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	
(Intercept)	-0.9677	0.1014	-9.5429								
log word frequency	-0.0094	0.0120	-0.7834	-0.0118	0.0851	0.0040	0.0003	0.6232	1	0.4299	n.s.
word length	0.1096	0.0037	29.6320	0.6026	44.8522	30.9949	0.3043	729.9822	1	0.0000	***
number of morphemes	0.0688	0.0138	4.9971	0.1070	1.5440	1.0367	0.0123	24.8583	1	0.0000	***
position	-0.0620	0.0228	-2.7243	-0.0431	0.4938	0.3617	0.0034	7.4318	1	0.0064	**
word class = verb (vs. noun)	0.0519	0.0152	3.4148	0.0553	0.7170	0.1966	0.0055	11.7037	1	0.0006	***
log speech rate	-0.2730	0.0255	-10.7077	-0.1945	8.0100	0.4569	0.0756	108.2420	1	0.0000	***

$n = 2\,017$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.5145$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.5682$

Table 37: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Hoocaq

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	
speaker	25	0.0579	-0.5013	0.2574	1.4977	1	0.221	n.s.
text	62	0.0838	-0.6998	1.6686	33.5262	1	0.000	***
Residual		0.2888						

N||ng

Table 38: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in N||ng

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-2.3787	0.0580	-40.9858							
log word frequency	-0.0857	0.0066	-12.9447	-0.1414	3.9417	3.8114	0.0268	164.9907	1	0.0000 ***
word length	0.1402	0.0038	37.1504	0.4544	37.8865	32.0627	0.1846	1236.9687	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.1216	0.0163	7.4768	0.0885	1.5692	1.4809	0.0090	55.6704	1	0.0000 ***
position	0.2285	0.0112	20.3994	0.2073	11.7731	8.9514	0.0633	401.9895	1	0.0000 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.0040	0.0096	-0.4181	-0.0045	-0.0080	-0.0057	0.0000	0.1759	1	0.6749 n.s.
log speech rate	-0.1231	0.0110	-11.1466	-0.1252	6.5637	-0.9150	0.0242	122.0875	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 5\,706$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.3745$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.4333$

Table 39: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in N||ng

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
speaker	7	0.0655	-0.8101	0.9553	29.6230	1	0 ***
text	33	0.0736	-0.0174	5.3171	163.2568	1	0 ***
Residual		0.3057					

Sakha

Table 40: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Sakha

	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	-1.8158	0.0569	-31.8993							
log word frequency	-0.0774	0.0057	-13.5460	-0.1927	5.7201	5.7505	0.0503	178.6419	1	0.0000 ***
word length	0.1267	0.0041	30.6876	0.5218	29.5126	27.5375	0.2130	830.8321	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	0.0427	0.0122	3.4973	0.0631	0.4411	0.2873	0.0035	12.2341	1	0.0005 ***
position	-0.0267	0.0159	-1.6763	-0.0208	0.0944	0.0368	0.0008	2.8224	1	0.0930 n.s.
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.0519	0.0129	-4.0329	-0.0631	0.5802	0.4443	0.0047	16.2679	1	0.0001 ***
log speech rate	-0.1882	0.0181	-10.3776	-0.1400	5.5948	2.1577	0.0364	104.8915	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 3\ 347, R_{(m)}^2 = 0.4773, R_{(c)}^2 = 0.5037$

Table 41: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Sakha

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
speaker	21	0.0591	0.5202	-0.2120	5.9555	1	0.0147 *
text	16	0.0269	-0.1371	0.1565	0.6059	1	0.4363 n.s.
Residual		0.2818					

Texistepec

Table 42: Summary of fixed effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Texistepec

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	β	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	s.-p. R^2	χ^2	df	p
(Intercept)	-2.0413	0.0791	-25.7930							
log word frequency	-0.0635	0.0108	-5.8663	-0.0959	1.6365	1.3517	0.0124	34.3605	1	0.0000 ***
word length	0.1501	0.0054	27.8689	0.5303	36.9072	37.3970	0.2200	682.7184	1	0.0000 ***
number of morphemes	-0.0469	0.0128	-3.6589	-0.0799	0.5960	0.7316	0.0049	13.3012	1	0.0003 ***
position	0.1563	0.0193	8.0796	0.1195	3.0774	3.2225	0.0231	64.5260	1	0.0000 ***
word class = verb (vs. noun)	-0.1931	0.0189	-10.2057	-0.2066	4.9379	4.8764	0.0362	102.4302	1	0.0000 ***
log speech rate	-0.1095	0.0160	-6.8638	-0.0995	2.2384	2.1305	0.0167	46.8450	1	0.0000 ***

$n = 2\,738$, $R_{(m)}^2 = 0.4313$, $R_{(c)}^2 = 0.4394$

Table 43: Summary of random effects of the linear mixed-effects model of word duration in Texistepec

Random effect	Groups	Std. Dev.	$\Delta R_{(m)}^2\%$	$\Delta R_{(c)}^2\%$	χ^2	df	p
text	6	0.0398	0.9241	2.7327	26.1752	1	0 ***
Residual		0.3326					